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Summary of novel methods to reduce accelerator impedance

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ABSTRACT

We review several important impedance-induced instabilities in circular lepton and hadron accelerators and modern approaches to analyse them. Specifically, we consider three representative large future accelerators, the FCC-ee, the High Luminosity LHC, and the FCC-hh projects as examples. We also survey some of the methods used to avoid, mitigate or suppress these instabilities, including some advanced beam feedback systems which are under development, and the possibility of coating the beam pipe with a high-temperature superconductor.

ARIES Consortium, 2020

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

One of the primary goals of future accelerator projects around the world is increasing the beam intensity. This means that also the self-induced electromagnetic fields will become stronger, possibly leading to a severe limitation of the machines' performances if no other actions were taken. Among these other actions, we include a thorough evaluation of impedance-induced instabilities, methods to reduce the coupling impedance with a proper choice of vacuum-chamber material, including coatings, and its geometry, and the development of novel feedback systems.

In this report, using as a reference two important APEC workshops, one held in September 2017 and the second one in September 2019, we briefly review some important impedance-induced instabilities, focusing our attention, in particular, on the lepton option of the Future Circular Collider (FCC-ee) and on the luminosity upgrade project of the LHC (High Luminosity LHC). We also survey methods applied to reduce accelerator impedances, and, finally, we discuss some advanced feedback systems and other mitigation techniques.

1. Introduction

ARIES is an Integrating Activity project which aims at developing European particle accelerator infrastructures in order to strengthen Europe's position in this field. Among the different projects sustained by ARIES, High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) has the goal of reaching an integrated luminosity 10 times higher than the present LHC, which requires a doubling of the beam intensity. The HL-LHC will be hosted in the same tunnel as the LHC and its operation programme is quite well defined for the next two decades. However, researches in the field of particle accelerators look further ahead, and CERN has started an exploratory study for a future long-term project centered on a new generation of circular colliders with a circumference of about 100 kilometers. The project is called Future Circular Collider (FCC) and the study, also sustained by ARIES, is exploring different options for accelerator projects in a global context, with emphasis on proton-proton and electron-positron high-energy frontier machines.

In this context, the ARIES Working Package 6, called APEC, Accelerator Performance and Concepts, is a networking activity which pushes to reach high performance in existing facilities and in future accelerators which are nowadays in the design stage. These objectives are pursued in several ways, which are combined and structured into separate tasks. Among them, task 6.4 reviews some of the existing strategies for the evaluation of beam-impedance effects and impedance models. Moreover, task 6.4 proposes and evaluates novel methods to reduce accelerator impedance by identifying strategies for their minimization and for the design of advanced beam feedback systems, in particular, related to future machines.

This ARIES task has been involved in the organization of some important workshops which addressed the topic of impedance-induced instabilities and their mitigation. In particular, in this report we will refer to the outcome of two such workshops:

1. **ARIES/ICFA joint mini-Workshop on Impedances and Beam Instabilities in Particle Accelerators** Benevento, Italy, 19-22 September 2017
(<http://prewww.unisannio.it/workshopwakefields2017/>)

2. **ARIES/ICFA joint mini-Workshop on Mitigation of Coherent Beam Instabilities in Particle Accelerators**, Zermatt, Switzerland, 23-27 September 2019
(<https://indico.cern.ch/e/MCBI2019/>)

In addition to highlighting key results from these ARIES workshops, in this report we will review, by way of example, the study of some selected instabilities and mitigation techniques performed for two particular machines: FCC-ee and LHC.

2. Review of some impedance-induced instabilities

An important workshop on “Impedances and Beam Instabilities in Particle Accelerators”, supported by ARIES, was held in Benevento (Italy) from 18 to 22 September 2017 and hosted by the University of Sannio.

The main goal of this workshop was to review the studies in the field of impedances and beam instabilities and to address recent advancements and breakthroughs. The workshop was divided into 5 sessions: impedance/wakefield theory and modeling, impedance measurements and control, instability theory and modeling, instability observations and cures, plus machine overviews.

In this chapter we mainly refer to the proceedings of the Benevento workshop and to the introductory talk presented at the second ARIES workshop on “Mitigation of Coherent Beam Instabilities in particle accelerators” held in 2019 at Zermatt.

Even though the first studies on impedance-induced instabilities were already developed in the mid/end 1960s, with the initial concepts regarding dispersion relations and coupling impedance described in the pioneering works of V. Vaccaro and A. M. Sessler [1, 2], this subject remains one of the main topics facing modern high performance accelerators, and it still represents a cutting-edge frontier in beam-physics research. The main reasons of the importance of these instabilities, that emerged from the Benevento workshop, can be summarized as following:

- The general trend in the design of new machines and in the upgrade of the existing ones is that of increasing the stored beam current with a consequent increase of self-induced electromagnetic fields.
- Several concepts related to wakefields and coupling impedances need to be adapted and extended to new types of accelerators, such as FELs and plasma wakefield accelerators [3].
- New phenomena observed in running machines need to be interpreted and addressed.
- New and future accelerators and also some upgrade programs of existing machines will explore new parameter regimes (not only higher beam current, but also higher brightness, higher beam energy etc.), which require novel and original approaches.
- There is a continuous progress in the modelling and understanding of impedance-induced beam instabilities, in particular thanks to the advancement of accelerator technology and to the dramatic increase of the available computing power.

- There is an intense and wide debate on open theoretical questions.

A clear conclusion which emerged from the workshop, was the necessity, for a reliable machine design or upgrade, to apply at least two out of three methods to achieve a trustworthy impedance estimation of each element to be installed: analytical model, accurate CAD/numerical simulations, and/or precise bench/laboratory measurements. This approach was originally established for the CERN ISR and also rigorously applied for the design of the LHC (where the impedance of each element was controlled by an “impedance police”).

This point was further stressed by different presentations that showed the good agreement between experimental data resulting from beam measurements and predictions given by the machine impedance model, for a wide range of accelerators, ranging from proton colliders to lepton factories.

In the following sections we will shortly review the classical concepts of wakefields and coupling impedances, while highlighting some recent improvements, and we will discuss the tools that nowadays are available to evaluate the impedance-induced instabilities. Finally, a short description of some important collective effects, useful for the understanding of the following chapters, will be presented.

2.1 WAKE FIELDS AND IMPEDANCE

When a beam of charged particles traverses a device, which is not a perfect conductor or is not smooth, it produces electromagnetic fields that perturb the following particles. Differently from the fields generated by external magnets and RF cavities, these ones depend on beam intensity, and their amplitude cannot be easily changed. These fields are generally described in time domain through the concept of wakefield, or, in frequency domain, by its Fourier transform, called coupling impedance. Their importance is due to the fact that, under some conditions, they can induce instabilities. Referring to Figure 2.1, let us consider two charges, a leading one (the source) q_1 , in the position (z_1, \vec{r}_1) , which, interacting with an accelerator device (the red shape that we suppose of cylindrical symmetry), produces an electromagnetic field and therefore a Lorentz force on a test charge q following at a distance $\Delta z = (z_1 - z)$ and with a transverse displacement from the ideal orbit \vec{r} .

Figure 2.1: Sketch used for the definition of wakefields.

With this geometry, by using the rigid beam approximation (the distance between the two charges remains constant inside a device) and the impulse approximation (what matters is the impulse imparted on the test charge), the effects of the longitudinal and transverse components of the Lorentz force can be separated. In the longitudinal plane the effect is summarised by an energy change:

$$U(\Delta z) = \int_{device} F_{\parallel} ds \rightarrow w_{\parallel}(\Delta z) = -\frac{U(\Delta z)}{qq_1} \quad (1)$$

while in the transverse plane we have a momentum kick

$$\vec{M}(\vec{r}, \Delta z) = \int_{device} F_{\perp} ds \rightarrow \vec{w}_{\perp}(\Delta z) = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\vec{M}(\vec{r}, \Delta z)}{qq_1} \quad (2)$$

Here w_{\parallel} and \vec{w}_{\perp} are defined as the longitudinal and the transverse dipole wake functions. For the transverse wake we have supposed a cylindrically symmetric structure and a velocity equal to the speed of light. For a non-circular geometry also another term, called quadrupolar wake field, would have been necessary. From the wake functions it is possible to obtain the coupling impedances as their Fourier transforms.

The determination of wake fields and coupling impedance is one of the first challenges in the evaluation of collective effects. It can be performed with analytical methods and by using 2D or 3D electromagnetic (em) codes. There exist several codes that solve the em problem in the frequency or in the time domain and that are used for the em design of accelerator devices, and new ones are continually developed:

- **ABCI**: Azimuthal Beam Cavity Interaction (<http://abci.kek.jp>)
- **MAFIA**: solution of Maxwell's equations by the Finite Integration Algorithm
- **CST Microwave Studio**: Computer Simulation Technology [4]
- **GdfidL**: Gitter drüber, fertig ist die Laube, literally: a simple way to build an harbour, is by putting up a mesh
- **ACE3P**: Advanced Computational Electromagnetic 3D Parallel software
- **Echo2D (3D)**: Electromagnetic Code for Handling Of Harmful Collective Effects
- **PBCI**: Parallel Beam Cavity Interaction.

Thanks to the tremendous computing resources available nowadays, these codes have become a fundamental tool that allows simulating realistic structures with an extremely high accuracy. The main problem of these codes remains that they do not determine the Green function of a structure, but only the wakefield of a bunch with a given longitudinal distribution (generally Gaussian). However, the tools used to study collective effects generally require, as input, the Green function of the whole machine. As a consequence, some manipulations of the results from these em codes is required before using them for beam dynamics studies. This problem, up to now, has not been completely solved, and there is no universal method yet that would allow entering the wake fields given by the em codes directly into the tracking codes.

On the other hand, analytical studies generally provide the electromagnetic fields for a point charge as source (the Green function), but they are limited to simplified structures and cannot be used for complicated realistic devices. However, also in this field the research evolution has brought about important results valid for some particular geometries [5]. For example, some papers have been published with analytical studies on the effect of resistive wall and space charge for an elliptic beam pipe [6]. In other cases, simple analytical structures can be used for checking the correctness of the results of em codes.

2.2 BEAM DYNAMICS SIMULATION TOOLS

In addition to analytical approaches, two kinds of simulation tools are generally used to study the behaviour of the beam under the influence of wakefields: particle-tracking simulation codes and Vlasov solvers.

The starting point for simulation codes is the equations of motion of a single charge, which are, in principle, quite simple. The inclusion of the effects of wakefield, also called beam induced voltage, however, couples the motion of different particles, and can be very tricky due to the possible introduction of numerical noise and non-physical phenomena.

The basic idea behind the numerical study of collective effects has not changed since the 1980s [7]. For example, for the longitudinal equations of motion of a single particle in a circular accelerator to be used in a simulation code, we assume, for simplicity, that the energy exchange between a charge and the surrounding accelerator environment is localized at a single place of the machine. The time step to be integrated is then generally the revolution period T_0 , (but in some cases, as in FCC, having a circumference of 100 km, we divide the machine into several sectors) and evaluate the variation of the charge's longitudinal position and energy with respect to the synchronous particle on every revolution period T_0 .

Let us consider, for simplicity, an energy exchange due only to the main RF system, qV_{RF} , the total wakefield, V_{wf} , and the synchrotron radiation. If we call ε the energy difference of a charge q with respect to the synchronous particle divided by the machine nominal energy E_s , its variation in T_0 can be written as

$$\Delta\varepsilon = \frac{qV_{RF}(\sin\phi - \sin\phi_s) - qV_{wf}(\phi) + R(T_0)}{E_s} - 2\frac{T_0}{\tau_s}\varepsilon \quad (3)$$

where V_{RF} is the RF peak voltage, $V_{wf}(\phi)$ the induced wake field voltage, $R(T_0)$ a stochastic variable changing each turn and taking into account the fact that the electromagnetic radiation occurs in quanta of discrete energy, and τ_s the longitudinal damping time. These last two terms are related to synchrotron radiation effects and they are important, in particular, in electron machines. The longitudinal position is identified by ϕ and ϕ_s , which are the phases, with respect to the RF voltage, of the charge q and of the synchronous particle, respectively. The value of ϕ_s depends on the acceleration and on the energy loss per turn due to synchrotron radiation. In the above equation, if necessary, it is possible to add terms due to other sources of energy change.

The other equation necessary for the longitudinal beam dynamics depends on the longitudinal position of the charge with respect to the synchronous particle, and its variation can be written as

$$\Delta(\phi - \phi_s) = -\frac{2\pi h\eta}{\beta^2} \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

where h is the RF harmonic number, η the slippage factor equal to $1/\gamma^2 - \alpha_c$ with γ the relativistic factor, α_c the momentum compaction, and β the ratio between the particle velocity and the speed of light. In the above equation we have assumed $\phi - \phi_s > 0$ for a particle behind the synchronous one, that is with positive time delay.

For the simulations, every bunch is modeled as an ensemble of particles, each one obeying the above two coupled equations, and the codes track these particles each time step. Since in a bunch the number of charges is in the range $10^8 - 10^{12}$ and, sometimes, even more, a very high computing power would be necessary, with the help of parallel clusters, to track all the particles. For this reason, generally, macro-particles, which gather together a given number of charges, are used. Nowadays, codes on personal PCs can run about 10^7 charges.

Without wakefield, the two equations can be easily calculated at each time step, and each macro-particle is independent of the others. The term which couples the equations of different particles, making the tracking more complicated, is the induced wakefield voltage $V_{WF}(\phi)$. It depends on the normalized longitudinal bunch distribution $\lambda(\phi)$ according to the relation

$$V_{wf}(\phi) = Q_{tot} \int_{bunch} d\phi' w_{\parallel}(\phi - \phi') \lambda(\phi') \quad (5)$$

with Q_{tot} the total charge of the bunch, and λ the normalized charge density. The convolution integral represents the energy gained or lost by a unity charge due to the wake field of the entire bunch (or rather the portion of the bunch in front of it). The above equation is valid only if we take into account the short-range wake fields, which influence the single turn beam dynamics (often also called single bunch beam dynamics). In order to include also the long-range wake fields for coupled bunch simulations, we should add a sum over previous bunches and turns in the above convolution integral.

Since in a simulation code we use macro-particles, the above integral is transformed into a summation, that is

$$V_{wf}(\phi_i) = \frac{Q_{tot}}{N_m} \sum_{j=1}^{N_m} w_{\parallel}(\phi_i - \phi_j) \quad (6)$$

with ϕ_i the longitudinal position of the i^{th} macro-particle and N_m the total number of macro-particles. The above equation has to be evaluated for each macro-particle at every integration step, requiring, only for the evaluation of the wake field, $(N_m - 1)N_m/2$ operations at every time step. In order to track $10^6 - 10^7$ macro-particles, at each time step more than 10^{11} operations are needed. In order to reduce the computing time and only in the evaluation of the wake field effects, the bunch is generally divided into N_s slices, or bins, each one containing n_i macro-particles. By supposing that

slices act as point charges, the induced voltage at the center of each slice is then evaluated by using the relation

$$V_{wf}(\phi_i) = \frac{Q_{tot}}{N_m} \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} n_j w_{\parallel}(\phi_i - \phi_j) \quad (7)$$

where in this case the indexes i and j refer to the bins and not to the macro-particles. To obtain the induced voltage for each macro-particle, an interpolation of the above equation is used.

Even if simulation codes are apparently easy to use, great care has to be taken for the determination of the machine wakefield needed as input in the codes, and for watching convergence studies depending on the number of macro-particles and/or the slices. In addition, it is important to identify and avoid non-physical results due to noise produced by the discretization with macro-particles.

At the other extreme with respect to simulation codes, we have Vlasov (or Fokker-Planck) solvers. In this case a continuous distribution function describing the motion of a beam, is considered as a superposition of coherent modes of oscillation. In the longitudinal plane, for example, by taking into account damping and fluctuations produced by the synchrotron radiation, we can write the following nonlinear integro-differential equation

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial q} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p} - \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial p} \frac{\partial H}{\partial q} = 2 \frac{T_0}{\tau_s} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} (p \Psi) + D \frac{\partial^2 \Psi}{\partial p^2} \quad (8)$$

where Ψ is the phase space longitudinal distribution, (q, p) are the canonical coordinates related to the position ϕ and to the relative energy ε respectively, H the Hamiltonian accounting for both the external fields and the collective force produced by the wake fields, and D a diffusion constant of the random process related to $R(T_0)$. If the right-hand side of the equation is zero, hypothesis valid, for example, with a good approximation for proton beams, we have the so-called Vlasov equation. The wake fields are included in the Hamiltonian.

There are two approaches to solve the above equation. As a first approach, it would seem that the equation could be treated by the usual methods for partial differential equations, through finite differences, which approximate the phase space longitudinal distribution function Ψ on nodes of a finite grid. However, such a technique fails because it does not preserve the symplectic form. Different and more appropriate methods must therefore be applied to preserve the symplectic structure of the equation.

Codes solving Vlasov-Fokker-Planck equations have been developed to study single bunch effects as alternative to multi-particle tracking codes, and they generally guarantee a very smooth evolution of the beam distribution function in time that allows reducing, and in some cases completely eliminating, the effect of numerical noise. Usually, the computing time for a simulation solving the Vlasov-Fokker-Planck equation is comparable to that of the multi-particle tracking codes. In any case, in order to calculate the collective force in the Hamiltonian term, the induced wake field voltage $V_{WF}(\phi)$ is calculated over a finite phase space grid.

A second and highly efficient method to study collective effects by solving the Vlasov equation is based on modal expansion and it is illustrated in the next sections together with a review of the theory of collective effects.

2.3 SINGLE-BUNCH COLLECTIVE EFFECTS

To simplify the beam dynamics study, it is generally convenient to distinguish between short range wakefields, which influence the single-turn (or single-bunch) beam dynamics, and long range wakefields, which last for many turns, are generated by resonant electromagnetic modes with high quality factors, are excited by one bunch or a train of bunches, and produce, under some conditions, coupled bunch instabilities (multi-turn or multi-bunch beam dynamics). In both cases a linear perturbation theory is generally used to analytically study these instabilities.

Let us first consider single-bunch effects at low intensity in the longitudinal plane. The wake field in this case produces a distortion of the distribution function that depends on the bunch current. There exists a bunch distribution which corresponds to the stationary solution of the Vlasov (for protons) or the Fokker-Planck equation (for electrons). There is a different behaviour between protons and electrons since, in the first case, we can neglect the effects of synchrotron radiation, and the bunch length and energy spread change with intensity in such a way as to preserve the longitudinal emittance. For electrons, instead, the energy spread remains constant, due to an equilibrium between radiation damping and quantum fluctuations noise, while the wakefield-induced potential well distortion changes the bunch length (and shape).

For both protons and electrons, we find an intensity threshold above which the longitudinal emittance (for protons) or the energy spread (for electrons) starts to increase. Above this threshold we are in the so-called microwave instability regime, characterised by an anomalous increase of bunch length and energy spread. This behaviour for electrons will be discussed in more detail in the next chapter dedicated to the FCC-ee collider since it represents, for that machine, one important source of instability.

The procedure used to solve the Vlasov equation for the single-bunch instabilities in the longitudinal plane can be summarized in the following steps (similar steps are also valid in the transverse plane):

- 1) use a perturbation method and write the phase space distribution as

$$\Psi(q, p; t) = \Psi_0(q, p) + \Delta\Psi(q, p; t) \quad (9)$$

- 2) use, as canonical longitudinal coordinates, the action-angle coordinates (I, ϕ) [possibly including the stationary potential-well distortion, e.g. Y. Cai, PRST-AB 14, 061002 (2011)] and consider the perturbation as sum of azimuthal coherent modes $R_m(I)$ oscillating with an unknown coherent frequency Ω :

$$\Delta\Psi(I, \phi; t) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} R_m(I) e^{im\phi} e^{-i\Omega t} \quad (10)$$

- 3) consider the instability produced by the wake fields excited only by the perturbation (not by the stationary distribution);
- 4) from the Vlasov equation, the so-called Sacherer integral equation is then obtained;
- 5) solve the integral equation: there are several methods to obtain the solution; for example, it is possible to expand each azimuthal mode $R_m(I)$ in terms of a set of orthonormal functions $g_{mk}(I)$ with unknown amplitude α_{mk} and a proper weight function $W(I)$ which depends on the derivative of the stationary distribution:

$$R_m(I) = W(I) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha_{mk} g_{mk}(I) \quad (11)$$

- 6) from the above equation an infinite set of linear equations is obtained; the eigenvalues represent the coherent frequencies and the eigenvectors the corresponding modes:

$$(\Omega - m\omega_s)\alpha_{mk} = \sum_{m'=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{k'=0}^{\infty} M_{kk'}^{mm'} \alpha_{m'k'} \quad (12)$$

For the transverse plane, following a similar procedure, we have this final eigenvalue system

$$(\Omega - \omega_\beta - m\omega_s)\alpha_{mk} = \sum_{m'=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{k'=0}^{\infty} M_{kk'}^{mm'} \alpha_{m'k'} \quad (13)$$

The matrix elements $M_{kk'}^{mm'}$ depend on the wakefield, beam and machine parameters. In the transverse plane they also depend on chromaticity. If the chromaticity is different from zero, single azimuthal modes can be unstable producing the so-called (transverse) head-tail instability. This is not an intensity threshold mechanism, and it is due to the coupling of the real part of the transverse impedance at negative frequency with the coherent modes shifted from the origin due to the chromaticity. It can be cured by adjusting the chromaticity and with the radiation damping.

At high intensities, mode coupling of different azimuthal modes can occur. In the longitudinal plane this is called microwave instability. Reliable prediction of microwave instability thresholds with Vlasov solvers and mode coupling theory may still be an open question, in particular for short bunches. Generally, simulation codes are considered more reliable. For FCC-ee, in both the cases of the main ring and the Booster, we predicted the threshold of this instability by using the PyHEADTAIL simulation code [8].

In case of long bunches in proton machines, the synchrotron tunes are in general much smaller than those in electron machines. Therefore, in some cases, the synchrotron period of protons can be neglected in the study of the instability because it is much longer than the instability growth times.

Moreover, the wavelength of the perturbation producing the instability is often of the size of the radius of the vacuum chamber, which is usually much shorter than the length of the proton bunch. Therefore, proton bunches, in some cases, can be viewed locally as coasting beams. For them we can then apply the Boussard criterion giving a threshold average current of

$$\frac{Q_{th}}{T_0} = I_{th} = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}|\eta|(E_s/e)\sigma_\varepsilon^2\sigma_z}{R|Z_{||}/n|} \quad (14)$$

where σ_ε is the RMS energy spread, σ_z the RMS bunch length, $|Z_{||}/n|$ the coupling impedance evaluated at the n th harmonic of the revolution frequency, and R the machine radius. In this case the microwave instability is not due to a mode coupling, but each single revolution harmonic it can be considered as an independent mode. The Boussard criterion can be a good indicator on how to cope with the microwave instability and where to act to mitigate such effect also for electron machines. For example, the increase of momentum compaction and of energy spread are effective means to increase the instability threshold. In the next chapter, we will see, for FCC-ee, that also the beamstrahlung makes an important contribution to increasing the microwave instability threshold. Moreover, for electrons, the Boussard criterion can be used to obtain the order of magnitude of the instability threshold.

The microwave instability does not produce beam losses, however it could be dangerous, in particular for colliding beams, since the bunch behaviour is not easy to predict in this regime. Synchrotron oscillations and a turbulent motion can occur, affecting the machine luminosity. In addition, we must say that no feedback system can yet be used for electron machines to counteract this instability.

For the transverse plane the instability due to mode coupling is even more dangerous since it produces beam losses. Vlasov solvers based on modal expansion in this plane are reliable and, for FCC-ee, we have evaluated the instability threshold by using the code DELPHI (Discrete Expansion over Laguerre Polynomials and Head-tail modes for Instabilities computation) [9]. A simplified expression to obtain the instability threshold for the transverse plane will be discussed in the Paragraph 3.1 with Eq. (19).

An advantage of the Vlasov solvers which use the modal expansion to study collective effects with respect to simulation codes is that they are able to predict instabilities also with very long rise times that would need too long simulations with tracking codes.

2.4 MULTI-BUNCH COLLECTIVE EFFECTS

For a machine like FCC-ee, due to the very high number of bunches (16640 for the low energy operation), it is not possible to use simulation codes in the multi-bunch regime. As a consequence, for the transverse case, the DELPHI Vlasov solver has been used, as will be discussed in the next chapter.

The analytical treatment is similar to the single-bunch case, with an additional index in the coherent modes taking into account the coupled-bunch oscillations. A simple analytical expression can be obtained by considering the lowest azimuthal mode $m = 0$ and a Gaussian bunch longitudinal distribution. The real part of the coupling impedance can produce stability or instability depending on the sign of the growth rate that can be written as

$$\alpha_{\mu\perp} = -\frac{cI}{4\pi(E_s/e)Q_\beta} \sum_{q=-\infty}^{\infty} \text{Re}[Z_\perp(\omega_q)] G_\perp(\sigma_\tau \omega'_q) \quad (15)$$

where c is the speed of light, I is the total beam current, Q_β is the betatron tune, σ_τ is the RMS bunch length in time, G_\perp is a form factor depending on bunch length and shape but that, for FCC-ee can be approximated with 1, and

$$\omega_q = \omega_0(qN_b + \mu + Q_\beta), \quad \omega'_q = \omega_q + \omega_0 \xi \frac{Q_\beta}{\eta} \quad (16)$$

with N_b the number of bunches, ξ the chromaticity, and ω_0 the revolution frequency.

In the above equations, μ represents the μ^{th} coupled bunch mode, which goes from 0 to $N_b - 1$. When $\alpha_{\mu\perp}$ is positive, the corresponding mode is unstable.

Let us consider, as transverse impedance, the resistive wall, that, for a circular pipe with an infinite thickness of a single layer can be written as

$$Z_\perp(\omega) = C \frac{Z_0}{2\pi b^3} [\text{sgn}(\omega) - i] \delta \quad \left(\frac{\chi c}{b} \ll \omega \ll \frac{c\chi^{-1/3}}{b} \right) \quad (17)$$

where $\chi = 1/(Z_0 \sigma_c b)$, Z_0 is the vacuum impedance, b is the pipe radius, δ is the material skin depth, namely $\delta = \sqrt{2/(\sigma_c \omega \mu)}$ with σ_c the pipe conductivity and μ the permeability; C is the machine circumference. It is important to observe that the frequency range of validity of the above equation is very wide, even if it depends on the vacuum chamber conductivity and radius. By considering, as example, a copper beam pipe with radius of 35 mm, the frequency f must be much greater than 1 Hz and much lower than 1 THz. The bunch spectrum corresponding to a bunch length of the order of mm, as that of FCC-ee, fully satisfies these constrains.

For completeness, and also because of its importance for the FCC-ee microwave instability, we here also give the longitudinal resistive wall impedance, valid under the same conditions

$$Z_\parallel(\omega) = C \frac{Z_0 \omega}{4\pi c b} [\text{sgn}(\omega) - i] \delta \quad (18)$$

We observe that $\text{Re}[Z_\perp(\omega)]$ depends on the sign of the frequency ω . Negative frequencies produce unstable modes with an exponential growth rate $\alpha_{\mu\perp}$, while positive ones give rise to damped oscillations. In addition to that, the transverse resistive wall impedance grows approximately with the

inverse of the square root of the frequency, determining the most dangerous coupled bunch mode when ω_q is as close to zero as possible.

This kind of instability leads to a loss of the beam if mitigation techniques, for example acting on the machine optics or recurring to feedback systems, are not used.

2.5 OUTCOME OF THE BENEVENTO WORKSHOP

The results presented in this Section as outcome of the Benevento workshop can be found in [5]. We can group them into four categories.

- 1) The first one concerns the beam coupling impedance. We here list the main conclusions:
 - During the design stage of a device for new or old accelerators, nowadays it is crucial to include also impedance minimization studies, possibly also accounting for other considerations stemming from multi-physics simulations associated with the impedance effects (such as heat deposition and stress analysis), as discussed in Chapter 4.
 - Nowadays we encounter an increased difficulty in the evaluation of beam coupling impedances of accelerators due to several factors:
 - Devices become more and more complicated and require ever more accurate electromagnetic descriptions;
 - Modern accelerators demand higher and higher performance in terms of beam characteristics and beam intensity, and this requires special attention to their impedance budgets. This in turn leads to the necessity of a very strict low impedance design policy.
 - New impedance regimes will be investigated in future accelerators (e.g. frequencies beyond 100 GHz, small structures, very long machines), where new phenomena may become important (e.g. surface roughness, anomalous skin effect, etc.).
 - Electromagnetic codes used to calculate the beam coupling impedance and the wake function nowadays use advanced computational techniques (such as the moving window) and are very powerful. This allows the detailed analysis of realistic structures that could not be efficiently simulated before.
 - Beam-based measurements are of fundamental importance to understanding and determining the limitations of running machines, in particular to identify:
 - Missing impedance contributions in the impedance model of a given machine;
 - Impedance contributions of newly installed structures by comparative measurements;
 - Non-conformities, malfunctioning or ageing equipment leading to a degradation of the structure with consequent increase of the impedance and possibly undesired effects on the beam;
 - Main contributors to the machine impedance and possible mitigation techniques and mitigation measures to reduce their impact on beam dynamics.

-
- 2) Once the impedance model of a machine has been obtained, the information would be meaningless if it could not be used in beam dynamics calculations for the evaluation of its impact on collective effects. Therefore, methods for the evaluation of beam instabilities were discussed and reviewed in detail. In particular we can define three methods:
- Vlasov solvers using modal analysis, such as those discussed in the previous sections, are widely employed to explore stability areas of complex machines in multi-dimensional parameter spaces. Their advantages and disadvantages were highlighted. Solvers of this type are
 - fast and suited for parameter scans;
 - able to reveal slowly growing modes;
 - usually based on approximations/simplifications that need to be kept in mind before drawing strong conclusions from their results, in particular due to the linear approximation generally used.
 - As already discussed in the previous sections, macro-particle simulations are also widely used and benefit from the increasing computing power that makes this approach more and more attractive. To summarize what was already discussed, they
 - are, in principle, simple to implement and to be extended to include several effects (e.g. feedback systems);
 - can take into account the full 6D phase space, and their results can be used for direct comparisons with beam measurements;
 - need an appropriate choice of the numerical parameters (number of slices, number of macro-particles) and convergence studies;

The main limitation is the computational power (memory, CPU time) and a time-limited observation window, which could not reveal slowly growing modes.
 - In addition to the methods already described in the previous sections, namely simulation codes and Vlasov solvers, two-particle models are still being used and extended to new cases (to include space charge, feedback systems, chromaticity). They are fairly simple and of great interest because they are capable of unveiling the basic physics mechanisms behind the instabilities.
- 3) Another important outcome of the workshop was the fact that, while the main source of beam instability is usually the machine beam coupling impedance, other mechanisms come into play and can affect instability thresholds. In particular there is a strong dependence of the threshold on:
- space charge: several models suggest that it acts against the onset of Transverse Mode Coupling Instability (TMCI), although some machine observations do not confirm this hypothesis. Besides, its influence on the loss of decoherence could play a detrimental role by helping coherent signals to remain long-lived. The influence of the space charge on the instability threshold is still an open question.
 - Beam-beam, electron cloud, ions: these effects can excite some coherent motions that couple not only different bunches, but also the head and tail of single bunches. On the other hand, they also introduce important betatron tune spreads that can counteract the onset of beam instabilities. Including these mechanisms in the wake/impedance formalism is not straightforward. However, the dynamics of these effects, together with the interplay between them and with the machine impedance, is in many cases

fundamental to build a global picture of beam stability. An important example of this, which will be discussed in the next chapter for FCC-ee, is the influence of the beamstrahlung on the microwave instability.

- 4) The last point of the Benevento workshop outcome is related to mitigation, which was also the main topic of the Zermatt workshop of 2019. Several mechanisms to suppress beam instabilities and, thereby, to extend machine performances were reviewed and illustrated, covering in particular the following subjects:
- Optimization of machine optics from the collective effects point of view. The optics provides the key to several parameters that can be used to reduce the sensitivity to coherent motion, in particular it is possible to:
 - set the proper tunes and linear chromaticities;
 - control the nonlinear chromaticity, (as, for example, the second order term Q'');
 - use octupoles to generate transverse amplitude detuning;
 - control the linear coupling, which can be beneficial, when transferring more stability from one transverse plane to the other, or detrimental, when it moves the coherent tunes out of the range for Landau damping;
 - change the transition energy.
 - Reliance on Landau damping by using conventional methods like octupole detuning or by exploring the efficiency of novel sources of betatron tune spread like Radio Frequency Quadrupole (RFQ) or electron lenses, which have not yet been used for this purpose in running machines, but hold a great promise for the upgrades and for future machines.
 - Use of feedback systems to damp coherent instabilities. Typically, the bandwidth of these systems has made them suitable to suppress coupled bunch instabilities of dipolar type, but they have remained inefficient against single-bunch instabilities with strong head-tail coupling for the transverse plane or in the microwave regime in the longitudinal plane. However, in their most cutting edge development, these systems have been demonstrated to be capable of damping transverse intra-bunch modes also for short proton bunches (which requires high bandwidth and a complex electronics chain) or quadrupolar type oscillations in the longitudinal plane (which requires special configuration of the hardware and could be of uttermost interest for machines like the CERN PS).

In conclusion, the subject of collective effects and impedance-induced instabilities in particle accelerators is very much alive, and the community highly motivated to exchange experience and to launch joint efforts in order to meet the challenging demands of future accelerators. Open questions still remain. However, we can observe a continuing progress on different fronts, and the promising outlook of many studies in terms of development and search for solutions, is a good sign for the success of future accelerators.

3. Collective effects for FCC lepton collider

In this chapter we present a study of impedance-induced instabilities for the lepton option of the Future Circular Collider (FCC-ee). This work related to the main collider rings is principally taken from the PhD thesis on “Coupling Impedance and Single Beam Collective Effects for the Future

Circular Collider (Lepton Option)” of E. Belli (E. Belli PhD thesis, ARIES monograph Vol. 53). In addition, some studies of beam instabilities in the full-energy booster ring are also included.

3.1 THE PROBLEM OF RESISTIVE WALL

The resistive wall impedance differs from the impedance of other machine devices, which, in some cases, can be optimized from the impedance point of view by using, for example, smooth transitions, higher-order modes damping systems and novel designs. For the resistive wall impedance, instead, the possibilities to reduce its impact on beam dynamics are more limited.

Referring to Eqs. (17) and (18), we see that the parameters that can be changed to reduce the two impedances are only the conductivity σ_c of the vacuum chamber (which could be made of copper, as in the case of the FCC-ee main rings, or with a thick copper coating, as in the case of the LHC [75 μm Cu layer]) and the beam pipe radius b . Concerning this last parameter, it cannot be increased too much because the electrical power required for the magnets would be too high. For FCC-ee, a value of $b = 35$ mm has been chosen, representing a good compromise also for the quadrupole magnets’ power. In addition to that, a thin coating with a material having a conductivity lower than that of copper is required to suppress the electron cloud build up, and this causes an increase of the value of the resistive wall impedance.

In order to highlight the importance of the resistive wall impedance in FCC-ee with respect to other colliders, and also as a reference for the beam dynamics studies reported in the following sections, the main parameters used to evaluate the effects of the wake fields are shown in Table I [10].

Let us first consider the longitudinal plane. From Table I we see two important peculiarities of this machine: the low energy spread, necessary to study very narrow particle resonances, and the very low momentum compaction, due to the low dispersion and the large machine circumference. This combination has a consequence for the microwave instability.

As a first rough approximation, the Boussard criterion, given by Eq. (14) can be used to obtain a scaling of the instability threshold. With the parameters of the lowest energy machine (operation on the Z boson resonance) and the nominal bunch population, the maximum allowed longitudinal broadband impedance $|Z_{\parallel}/n|$ to avoid the instability is about 0.66 m Ω , about 100 times lower than for the LHC, which is highly demanding even for a very large machine like the FCC. As a consequence, in order to operate at nominal current below the microwave instability regime, a careful design of all the different devices is needed, with the aim of minimizing the impact on the coupling impedance.

This optimization activity is a task which is generally performed in all new accelerators, and also in the existing one for machine upgrades. However, the main difference of FCC-ee with respect to other colliders is the large circumference of $C = 97.756$ km. From Eqs. (17) and (18), the resistive wall impedance is proportional to C . This property is not true for other machine devices, i.e., bellows, rf cavities, etc. For example, the number of bellows in an accelerator is not proportional to the machine length: the total number of bellows in KEKB, whose circumference is 3 km, is about 1000, while FCC-ee needs about 8000 bellows, despite a 30 times larger circumference.

As a consequence, by increasing the machine length, the contribution of the resistive wall impedance with respect to the other devices grows in importance, becoming critical for the microwave instability.

In the transverse plane too, the resistive wall gives a low single-bunch instability threshold. The use of Eq. (13) for the transverse single bunch instabilities (TMCI) will be discussed in the following section. Here we use a simple expression derived from the approximate evaluation of the tune shift of the zero azimuthal coherent mode. When this is equal to minus the synchrotron tune, the azimuthal mode zero couples with mode -1, so that we are in the transverse mode coupling instability regime.

The corresponding threshold can be written as

$$N_{th} = \frac{4\pi(E_s/e)\tau_b Q_s}{e\bar{\beta}\text{Im}[Z_{m,\perp}^{eff}]} \quad (19)$$

where m is the mode number, $\tau_b = 4\sigma_\tau$ is the full bunch length in time, $\bar{\beta}$ is the average beta of the machine and $Z_{m,\perp}^{eff}$ is the effective transverse impedance given by

$$Z_{m,\perp}^{eff} = \frac{\sum_{p=-\infty}^{\infty} Z_{\perp}(\omega_p) h_m(\omega_p - \omega_\xi)}{\sum_{p=-\infty}^{\infty} h_m(\omega_p - \omega_\xi)} \quad (20)$$

which represents the transverse impedance Z_{\perp} averaged over the bunch power spectrum of azimuthal mode m , which, for a Gaussian bunch, is given by

$$h_m(\omega) = (\omega\sigma_\tau)^{2|m|} e^{-\omega^2\sigma_\tau^2} \quad (21)$$

and $\omega_\xi = \omega_0\xi/\eta$ and $\omega_p = (p + \Delta Q_\beta)\omega_0 + m\omega_s$, where ΔQ_β is the fractional part of the betatron tune. The maximum allowed effective transverse impedance to avoid the instability can be obtained from Eq. (19) and in the FCC-ee at the Z resonance it is about 425 kΩ/m, using the natural bunch length without any blow up due to beamstrahlung. By considering a Gaussian bunch of nominal length and only the transverse impedance due to the resistive wall, for a copper pipe with 35 mm radius and without coating, the effective transverse impedance is about 155 kΩ/m, only a factor of 2.7 below the instability threshold.

This conclusion, obtained here by using approximate expressions, will be confirmed in the next sections with more accurate simulations.

Table I: Machine and beam parameters of the FCC-ee for different beam energies. Bunch length and energy spread are cited for noncolliding beams with synchrotron radiation ("SR") in the arcs only and for colliding bunches that are also

subject to beamstrahlung (“BS”). The abbreviation “DA” refers to the dynamic aperture. ^b relative to the geometrical strength $k_2 = (\theta \beta_y^* \beta_{y,sext})^{-1} \sqrt{\beta_x^* / \beta_{x,sext}}$.

	Z	WW	ZH	tt	
Circumference (km)	97.756				
Bending radius (km)	10.760				
Free length to IP ℓ^* (m)	2.2				
Solenoid field at IP (T)	2.0				
Full crossing angle at IP θ (mrad)	30				
SR power / beam (MW)	50				
Beam energy (GeV)	45.6	80	120	175	182.5
Beam current (mA)	1390	147	29	6.4	5.4
Bunches / beam	16640	2000	328	59	48
Average bunch spacing (ns)	19.6	163	994	2763 ^a	3396 ^a
Bunch population (10^{11})	1.7	1.5	1.8	2.2	2.3
Horizontal emittance ϵ_x (nm)	0.27	0.84	0.63	1.34	1.46
Vertical emittance ϵ_y (pm)	1.0	1.7	1.3	2.7	2.9
Arc cell phase advances (deg)	60/60		90/90		
Momentum compaction α_p (10^{-6})	14.8		7.3		
Arc sextupole families	208		292		
Horizontal β_x^* (m)	0.15	0.2	0.3	1.0	
Vertical β_y^* (mm)	0.8	1.0	1.0	1.6	
Horizontal size at IP σ_x^* (μ m)	6.4	13.0	13.7	36.7	38.2
Vertical size at IP σ_y^* (nm)	28	41	36	66	68
Energy spread (SR/BS) σ_δ (%)	0.038/0.132	0.066/0.131	0.099/0.165	0.144/0.186	0.150/0.192
Bunch length (SR/BS) σ_z (mm)	3.5/12.1	3.0/6.0	3.15/5.3	2.01/2.62	1.97/2.54
Piwinski angle (SR/BS) ϕ	8.2/28.5	3.5/7.0	3.4/5.8	0.8/1.1	0.8/1.0
Length of interaction area L_i (mm)	0.42	0.85	0.90	1.8	1.8
Hourglass factor R_{HG}	0.95	0.89	0.88	0.84	0.84
Crab sextupole strength ^b (%)	97	87	80	40	40
Energy loss / turn (GeV)	0.036	0.34	1.72	7.8	9.2
RF frequency (MHz)	400			400 / 800	
RF voltage (GV)	0.1	0.75	2.0	4.0 / 5.4	4.0 / 6.9
Synchrotron tune Q_s	0.0250	0.0506	0.0358	0.0818	0.0872
Longitudinal damping time (turns)	1273	236	70.3	23.1	20.4
RF bucket height (%)	1.9	3.5	2.3	3.36	3.36
Energy acceptance (DA) (%)	± 1.3	± 1.3	± 1.7	$-2.8 + 2.4$	

The problem of the resistive wall impedance is even more accentuated by the fact that a thin layer of coating is foreseen to reduce the secondary electron yield (SEY) for electron cloud mitigation and, in

some cases, to help the pumping process. The presence of this film makes the surface resistance of the beam pipe higher than pure copper, and the resistive wall effect is more pronounced. Moreover, the uncertainty on the coating conductivity varying with frequency may give inaccurate results of instability thresholds. A thorough study of the resistive wall impedance for a two-layer system has been performed in [11], where it is shown that, in the case of FCC-ee, the dominant effect on beam dynamics mainly comes from the thickness of the coating while its conductivity only plays a marginal role. Therefore, the best way to decrease the resistive wall contribution is to reduce the coating thickness. Indeed, it has been demonstrated that, for a good conductor, if the skin depth of the coating material is much larger than its thickness, then the transverse and longitudinal impedances of a two-layer system can be written as [11]

$$Z_{\perp}(\omega) = C \frac{Z_0}{2\pi b^3} \left\{ [sgn(\omega) - i]\delta_2 - 2i\Delta \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} \right) \right\} \quad (22)$$

$$Z_{\parallel}(\omega) = C \frac{Z_0 \omega}{4\pi c b} \left\{ [sgn(\omega) - i]\delta_2 - 2i\Delta \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} \right) \right\} \quad (23)$$

where δ_2 is the skin depth of the substrate, Δ the coating thickness, σ_1 and σ_2 the conductivities of the two materials. In the above equations, the first term in the brackets is the impedance of a single layer, as shown in Eqs. (17) and (18). If $\sigma_1 \ll \sigma_2$ (a good conductivity of the substrate), both the impedances, with respect to the single layer, have an additional imaginary term which does not depend on the conductivity of the substrate (no matter what kind of coating is used) and, if the conductivity of the coating is much worse than the one of the substrate, it is directly proportional to the coating thickness.

This last observation has an important implication because, in order to reduce the resistive wall impedance in a two-layer system, with a first layer coating used to mitigate the electron cloud effect and to help the pumping process, it is important to focus the attention on the minimum thickness that can be reached without compromising the performance of the material in terms of SEY. The strategy proposed to mitigate the electron cloud build up in the main rings of FCC-ee is to lower the SEY of the beam pipe walls by applying a coating of non-evaporable getters (NEG), an alloy of the three metals Ti, Zr and V. Due to the results obtained for the resistive wall impedance with two layers, an extensive measurement campaign was performed at CERN to characterize TiZrV films with thicknesses below 250 nm, with the purpose of finding the minimum effective thickness satisfying vacuum and electron cloud requirements. A thickness of 100 nm was found and proposed as a compromise between impedance minimization and electron cloud requests [12,13].

3.2 THE IMPEDANCE BUDGET

One important question about the resistive wall impedance is related to the choice of the beam pipe shape. Initially an elliptic geometry was proposed [14]. However, the elliptic pipe presented two main problems. First, it produces quite a large incoherent betatron tune shift due to the quadrupolar resistive wall wake fields. Indeed, a rough estimation of the possible effect of an elliptic chamber with semi-axes of 35x60 mm provided a tune shift of about ± 0.27 times the beam current in units of Ampere. This means that during the beam injection and ramp-up to the nominal current of 1.39 A, the tune variation is about 0.38. In order to cope with such a big tune change, additional feedback systems would be necessary to keep the tune constant as required by the beam-beam interaction, dynamic aperture considerations and other beam dynamics issues.

The other reason for the choice of the circular shape was related to the necessity to insert synchrotron radiation (SR) absorbers to localize the impact of the synchrotron radiation fans and to facilitate the corresponding cooling and shielding. Due to their large number, SR absorbers may represent a very important source of impedance. Indeed, with the initial choice of an elliptic pipe, the absorbers were positioned on one side of the major semi-axis, as in the left hand-side of Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: 3D model of the FCC-ee chamber and a SR absorber. Left, old proposal, right, new proposal.

However, this choice gave rise to high wakefields, even larger than those from the resistive wall [14]. As a consequence, the final shape of the vacuum chamber was chosen to be circular with 35 mm radius and two narrow rectangular antechambers on both sides (winglets). Absorbers will then be installed inside the chamber winglets, every 4-6 meters along the beam line, as shown on the right-hand side of Figure 3.1, with the purpose of intercepting the radiation that, otherwise, would impact on the beam chamber proper. These metallic devices are shaped like a trapezoid, with a total length of 30 cm and placed at about 42.5 mm from the beam axis. Placing slots for vacuum pumps just in front of each absorber allows to efficiently capture the molecule desorption. The pumping slots have a racetrack profile, length of 100-120 mm and width of 4-6 mm. Behind the slots, a cylindrical volume and a flange will be installed to support a NEG pump. Numerical simulations of the beam chamber profile with one absorber insertion have been performed using CST. These impedance studies do not include pumping slots and pumps. These simulations show that below 3 GHz the longitudinal impedance is purely inductive, giving a longitudinal broadband impedance $Z_{\parallel}/n \approx 1 \text{ m}\Omega$ for 10000 absorbers in the ring.

Other devices have been studied and optimized from the impedance point of view for FCC-ee. In particular, in Figure 3.2, not to scale, we show the RF tapers and cavities, in Figure 3.3 the horizontal

and vertical collimators, in Figure 3.4 the Beam Position Monitors (BPM), while, in Figure 3.5, we have sketched the bellows with the RF fingers.

Figure 3.2: Sketch, not to scale, of a group of 4 RF cells with tapers. The taper-out corresponds to the transition from radius $a = 50$ mm outside the cryomodule to radius $b = 150$ mm inside the cryomodule and vice versa for the taper-in. The taper length is $g=0.5$ m.

Figure 3.3: Perspective view of the vertical collimator (left side) and top view of the horizontal one (right side).

Figure 3.4: Perspective view of the four-button BPM (left side) and CST model of the winglet-to-circular taper for BPM installation (right side).

Figure 3.5: Conventional finger-type RF shielding (left side) and inside view of the new comb-type bellows with small fingers between the teeth [SuperKEKB design] (right side).

In particular, for what concerns the BPM, in order to push the higher-order modes trapped in the structure to higher frequencies, a design with a conical button, similar to the one used in SIRIUS [15], was studied. Because of the particular shape of the vacuum chamber in the arcs, a special type of winglet-to-circular tapers shown on the right-hand side of Figure 3.4 was initially designed. However, the contribution of these special tapers to the impedance budget turned out to be very large and comparable to the resistive wall one. Therefore, BPMs will be installed directly on the beam pipe with a rotation angle of 45° .

Finally, for the bellows with RF shielding, it was found that the conventional finger-type RF shielding shown on the left-hand side of Figure 3.5 gave a non-negligible impedance contribution compared to the resistive wall one. Therefore, it was decided to use comb-type bellows and flanges similar to those of SuperKEKB [16] shown on the right-hand side of Figure 3.5. In this case, the RF shielding consists of nested teeth with 10 mm length, 1 mm width, 0.5 mm radial thickness and 2.14 mm gap between adjacent teeth, corresponding to a gap of 0.57 mm between the nested teeth. This design also includes small fingers to ensure electrical contacts.

The contribution of all the above machine components to the longitudinal impedance budget has been evaluated by means of ABCI [17] and CST electromagnetic simulations. In Table II we have summarized the loss factor, defined as the energy lost by a charge due to the wake field of the entire bunch, and the power losses for the different devices at nominal intensity and bunch length, in the lowest energy case of 45.6 GeV. As already discussed, the main contribution is given by the resistive wall with about 58% of the total power losses.

As already discussed in the Section 2.1 on wake fields and impedance, both the codes ABCI and CST do not allow obtaining a wake field that can be used directly in beam dynamics simulation codes, since they do not give the Green function, but only the wake potential of a given longitudinal distribution. For example, in Figure 3.6 we show the longitudinal wake potentials of a 3.5 mm Gaussian bunch produced by each component compared to the resistive wall contribution with a 100 nm NEG coating.

Table II: Power loss of the main FCC-ee components at nominal intensity and bunch length (without the blow up due to beamstrahlung), in the lowest energy case of 45.6 GeV.

Component	Number	k_{loss} [V/pC]	P_{loss} [MW]
Resistive wall	97.75km	210	7.95
Collimators	20	18.7	0.7
RF cavities	56	18.5	0.7
RF double tapers	14	26.6	1.0
BPMs	4000	40.1	1.5
Bellows	8000	49.0	1.8
Total		362.9	13.7

Figure 3.6: Longitudinal wake potentials for a 3.5 mm Gaussian bunch due to the main FCC-ee components compared with the resistive wall contribution with a 100 nm NEG coating (blue line).

This wake potential cannot be used in simulation codes. As a consequence, for beam dynamics studies, the wake potential of a 0.35 mm Gaussian bunch, corresponding to 1/10 of the zero current bunch length without considering the beamstrahlung, has been considered as Green function for PyHEADTAIL tracking simulations. We have checked that in this way it was possible to reconstruct the wake potential of the nominal bunch length in simulations, obtaining the same result as the electromagnetic codes. As an example, in Figure 3.7 we show the direct wake potential given by CST compared with that reconstructed by PyHEADTAIL for a single BPM.

Figure 3.7: Comparison of the longitudinal wake potentials of a 3.5 mm Gaussian bunch obtained with CST with the wake potentials obtained from PyHEADTAIL as a convolution between the longitudinal bunch distribution and the wake potential of a 0.35 mm Gaussian bunch for a BPM.

3.3 COLLECTIVE EFFECTS IN THE MAIN RINGS

For the study of collective effects and impedance-induced instabilities for FCC-ee, we have focused the work on the single bunch longitudinal dynamics because it resulted in the most critical case. Bunch length and energy spread as a function of beam intensity are shown in Figures 3.8 and 3.9. They are obtained from PyHEADTAIL simulations taking into account the wake potential of 0.35 mm Gaussian bunch as discussed in the previous section. From the blue curves, obtained with the beam parameters without beamstrahlung, we observe that the microwave instability threshold, which is where the energy spread starts to increase, is found at a bunch population of about 2.5×10^{11} . This threshold is dangerously close to the nominal intensity of 1.7×10^{11} , leaving a very small safety margin.

However, with the red curves we have also reported the results of the simulations by considering the beamstrahlung, which is the radiation effect from one beam caused by its interaction with the electromagnetic field of the other beam. The beamstrahlung produces an increase of the nominal bunch length and energy spread by a factor of about 3.5. If we consider this mechanism independently of the impedance-induced instabilities, then there is a clear mitigation effect: the energy spread remains constant and equal to the nominal one, and the bunch length changes by a small fraction due to the potential well distortion up to a bunch population of 5×10^{11} . This important mitigation effect due to the collision of the beams deserves further investigations. In particular, we should take into account, in a self-consistent way, also collective effects to study the possible interaction between the two mechanisms.

Figure 3.8: RMS bunch length as a function of the bunch population with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) beamstrahlung, by considering the impedance contribution of all the machine components.

Figure 3.9: RMS energy spread as a function of the bunch population with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) beamstrahlung, by considering the impedance contribution of all the machine components.

For what concerns the single bunch dynamics in the transverse plane, as a first estimation we have taken into account only the resistive wall impedance and have studied the TMCI by solving an eigenvalue system like that given in Eq. (13) by means of DELPHI, a semi-analytic Vlasov solver which computes eigenfrequencies (tune shifts and growth rates) of coherent transverse oscillation modes for a given coupling-impedance, in the mode-coupling regime, taking into account azimuthal and radial modes expanded into orthogonal Laguerre polynomials. As already discussed in Section 3.1, TMCI occurs when the frequencies of two neighboring modes are merging. Unlike the microwave instability in the longitudinal plane, above the transverse instability threshold the bunch is lost, and this makes the TMCI very dangerous for the beam. The TMCI studies take into account the bunch lengthening due to the potential well distortion at different intensities, given by PyHEADTAIL, always assuming a Gaussian distribution.

Figure 3.10 shows the real part of the tune shift of the first two radial modes, with azimuthal number going from -2 to 2, as a function of the bunch population, in the case of NEG coating with 100 nm thickness. We can see that the TMCI threshold is a factor of about 2.6 higher than the nominal bunch intensity, similar to what was predicted in Section 3.1.

Figure 3.10: Real part of the tune shift of the first coherent oscillation modes as a function of the bunch population for 100 nm thickness of NEG coating. The curve is obtained with DELPHI code by using the machine parameters of Table 1 at the Z resonance and the bunch lengths obtained from PyHEADTAIL at different intensities. The dashed line represents the nominal bunch population.

The effect of the transverse resistive wall impedance concerns also the multi-bunch dynamics, here producing a transverse coupled-bunch instability (TCBI). For an evaluation of this instability, we have used Eq. (15). In Section 2.4 we have already concluded that the most dangerous coupled bunch mode is the one with coherent frequency ω_q closest to zero and negative. By considering, for example, again the FCC-ee beam parameters on the Z resonance and $q = -1$, and by defining as Q_0 and ΔQ_β the integer part and the fractional part of the betatron tune, respectively, i.e. $Q_\beta = Q_0 + \Delta Q_\beta$, the most dangerous coupled bunch mode can be obtained from Eq. (16) when $\mu = N_b - Q_0 - 1 = 16370$, and its lowest negative frequency is equal to $\omega_q = -\omega_0(1 - \Delta Q_\beta)$. By considering in Eq. (15) a single betatron frequency line instead of the sum over q , for the vertical plane with a fractional part of the tune of $\Delta Q_\beta = 0.22$, the growth rate of the most dangerous mode is about 435 s^{-1} , corresponding to a rise time of 2.3 ms, i.e. 7 machine turns. This value must be compared to the transverse radiation damping time of 0.83 s, corresponding to 2550 turns, that is much longer than required for instability suppression. Figure 3.11, left side shows the beam spectral lines of three coupled bunch modes and the real part of the transverse impedance due to the resistive wall close to zero frequency, while Figure 3.11, right side, shows the growth rate as a function of the coupled bunch mode number, highlighting the presence of several unstable modes that need to be damped.

The rise times of these modes are in the range of few milliseconds, which are usually cured by transverse bunch by bunch feedback systems in other lepton factories. However, in the case of FCC-ee, these rise times correspond to only a few turns due to the large circumference of the machine and a new challenging feedback system is required. Some schemes to cope with this fast and dangerous instability are discussed in Section 5.1.

Figure 3.11: Vertical coupled bunch spectrum at Z resonance and real part of the resistive wall impedance as a function of frequency around zero frequency (left), and growth rate of the coupled bunch modes as a function of azimuthal mode number $m = 0$ (right).

A last impedance-induced instability that has been considered for the main rings of FCC-ee is the longitudinal coupled bunch instability. This instability is produced by trapped high-quality resonant modes (HOMs). A very interesting study about the determination of trapped modes in the interaction region of the FCC-ee and mitigation by means of optimization design and HOM absorbers can be found in [18]. However, except for very particular devices, generally it is not possible to predict exact locations and especially the precise frequencies of trapped modes. Therefore, we have determined the maximum HOM impedance as a function of its resonance frequency, such that the corresponding growth rate is exactly balanced by the natural radiation damping. As for the transverse plane, also in this case the development of a feedback system is required for safe operation.

Before concluding this section, we want to briefly mention the study related to the $t\bar{t}$ option of FCC-ee (highest energy). There were two main concerns about this configuration of the machine:

- 1) To reach such a high energy, a double RF system is foreseen with 400 and 800 MHz RF cavity system. What is the contribution of the total RF system to the longitudinal coupling impedance?
- 2) The bunch length at $t\bar{t}$ is only slightly affected by the beamstrahlung, and we have just seen that for the Z pole this is an important effect that mitigates the microwave instability.

Despite the above concerns, the TMCI and the microwave instability do not seem to be dangerous for the FCC-ee at the $t\bar{t}$ energy. Indeed, the much higher energy and energy spread compensate by far the other parameters, and preliminary studies [19] demonstrate that the thresholds for this machine are much higher than those for the Z pole.

3.4 COLLECTIVE EFFECTS IN THE BOOSTER

In order to sustain the short beam lifetime foreseen for FCC-ee, a full-energy booster, installed in the same collider tunnel, will provide continuous top-up injection, in addition to initially filling the main rings of FCC-ee. Having the same circumference, the booster will pose the same impedance problems as the main rings in terms of resistive wall. Moreover, in order to not affect the collider luminosity and to diminish the background generated by lost particles, the booster is expected to provide, at extraction, an equilibrium transverse emittance similar to the one in the collider. The relatively high nominal intensity of 3.4×10^{10} particles per bunch (ppb), though much smaller than for the collider rings, could lead to collective effects which might severely limit the booster operation. This is because the booster beam pipe is foreseen to be made from stainless steel with a radius $r_c = 25$ mm. With respect to FCC-ee, here we face both a reduced pipe radius and the much poorer conductivity of stainless steel, which together could induce strong instabilities in both longitudinal and transverse planes.

Indeed, by using the parameter list of Table III, an intensity threshold of 0.1×10^{10} ppb, significantly lower than the nominal intensity, was found for the microwave instability at injection into the booster. In the transverse plane, the intensity threshold due to transverse mode-coupling instability was 0.6×10^{10} ppb [20]. Of course, these values are unacceptable and some methods to reduce the impedance and increase the instability thresholds have to be investigated.

Table III: Machine and beam parameters of the FCC-ee booster.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Machine circumference (C_r)	97.756 km	SR 1 σ bunch length (σ_{z0})	1.26 mm
Beam energy at injection (E_0)	20 GeV	RF frequency (f_{rf})	400 MHz
Beam rev. frequency at injection (f_0)	3.06 kHz	Harmonic number (h)	130432
Bunch population (N_b^{nom})	3.4×10^{10} ppb	RF voltage (V_{rf})	60 MV
Number of bunches per beam (M_b)	16640	Arc phase advance (ϕ_a)	60°
SR 1 σ rel. energy spread ($\sigma_{dE0,r}$)	0.166×10^{-3}	Mom. comp. factor (α_c)	1.48×10^{-5}
SR energy loss per turn (U_0)	1.33 MeV	Synchrotron tune (Q_s)	0.0304
SR damping time (τ_z)	15013 turns	Betatron tunes ($Q_{x,y}^{nom}$)	269.139

In order to significantly reduce the resistive wall impedance, the possibility of applying a copper coating to the beam-pipe was investigated, similar to what has been done for the LHC. In Figure 3.12 the longitudinal and transverse resistive wall impedances of a two-layer vacuum chamber, with the external layer in stainless steel and the internal layer in copper with variable thickness, is shown. The

plots show the interesting feature that, for a given thickness, both longitudinal and transverse impedances converge to the single-layer stainless-steel and copper impedances respectively for low and high frequencies. Finally, it should be noted that, since the booster is a fast-cycling machine, eddy currents in presence of a copper layer could be an issue during acceleration and their effects should be separately investigated.

Figure 3.12: Longitudinal (top) and transverse dipolar (bottom) resistive wall impedance as a function of frequency in the FCC-ee booster with a beam-pipe in stainless steel and an inner copper coating with different values of thickness. The five vertical dashed lines mark the frequencies above which the corresponding impedances converge to the single-layer copper impedance.

Figure 3.13 shows the rms relative energy spread and bunch length as a function of the bunch population. As can be seen from the figures, a thickness larger than 1 μm does not affect the threshold anymore. This can be considered the minimum thickness of the copper coating to reduce the resistive wall impedance and mitigate the microwave instability. However, the threshold is still much lower than the nominal bunch intensity. Unless we increase the beam pipe radius, there are no other obvious actions that can be taken to reduce the resistive wall impedance.

However, it is still possible to mitigate the instability by acting on the beam parameters. By increasing the nominal energy spread, from the Boussard criterion given by Eq. (14), we have a tool to strongly affect the microwave instability threshold. This can be achieved in the booster by using wigglers.

They have the double advantage of increasing the nominal energy spread and bunch length and to reduce the radiation damping times, which also help in mitigating collective effects.

Figure 3.13: Rms relative energy spread (top) and bunch length (bottom) as a function of bunch population for different values of copper thickness. In both images the yellow and cyan curves are completely overlapped.

In Figure 3.14 we have reported the intensity thresholds as a function of different values of energy lost by synchrotron radiation U_0 , which is inversely proportional to the longitudinal damping time τ_z and proportional to the square of the energy spread.

As impedance, we have used the resistive wall one with a copper layer of 1 μm . The plots show that U_0 should be at least 4 MeV in order not to encounter the microwave instability for the nominal bunch intensity. This is in full agreement with the current machine design plan. Indeed, from considerations entirely concerning the transverse plane, the installation of 16 wigglers able to provide $U_0 = 126$ MeV is foreseen [10].

Figure 3.14: Equilibrium rms relative energy spread (top) and bunch length (bottom), in the FCC-ee booster at injection, as a function of bunch population for different values of energy lost per turn due to synchrotron radiation.

Under the same conditions, that is $1 \mu\text{m}$ of copper layer and 4 MeV of energy lost by radiation, we are able to also mitigate the transverse mode coupling instability. Indeed, from the DELPHI code, no mode coupling is observed up to 5×10^{10} ppb [21]. Finally, for what concerns the transverse resistive wall coupled bunch instability, the largest growth rate corresponds to about 1-2 turns, even much faster than in the collider rings. These rise-times are shorter by several orders of magnitude than the transverse radiation damping. A novel challenging feedback system is needed which is able to act on the short time of one revolution turn, as that presented in Section 5.1.

4. Methods to reduce the impedance for the HL-LHC and for FCC-hh

At CERN, two projects foresee major upgrades of the existing particle accelerators: the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) [22] and the LHC Injectors Upgrade (LIU) [23]. In this context, beam intensity and stored beam energy will be doubled. Some of the current accelerator

components cannot safely perform their main task with these new conditions. As an example, it was demonstrated that the majority of the devices responsible for partially or totally absorbing the beam, the so-called beam intercepting devices or BIDs (dumps, collimators, absorbers/scrapers etc.), have to be redesigned to face the new challenging scenario.

These devices, because of their specific functional requirements, usually, are among the strongest impedance sources in CERN accelerators. Thus, an impedance minimization campaign for the new BIDs was started, and this chapter reports some results of this campaign. In particular, we define a series of guidelines to minimize the device impedance and present some examples of the successful application of these guidelines in the context of LIU project. Furthermore, the thermo-mechanical effects due to impedance-induced heating are also discussed, and a method to simulate these is reviewed.

4.1 GUIDELINES FOR THE MECHANICAL DESIGN OF LOW IMPEDANCE DEVICES

This section discusses some common mechanical high impedance features in accelerator components and the way to cure them. In particular, the high geometric impedance of some devices is discussed and a possible simple and cost-effective design modification to reduce its detrimental impact is proposed. These methods are generally well known in the community working on coupling impedances, but it is important to communicate and spread these guidelines also among the mechanical engineers working on the design of the components.

Abrupt Changes of Cross Section

Abrupt changes of vacuum-chamber cross sections should be avoided because they generate electromagnetic trapped modes visible as well-defined peaks in the impedance curve, as shown on the left side of Figure 4.1.

In order to investigate the effects of the abrupt changes of cross section, the geometry shown on the right side of Figure 4.1 was simulated. The radius of the small pipe was considered fixed ($r_a = 5$ mm) while the radius of the larger pipe, r_b was parametrized. The longitudinal impedance of the abrupt change of section is reported in Figure 4.1 left side, for different value of the radius r_b . Compared to the case $r_a = r_b$, i.e. no section change, for $r_b > r_a$ an increase in the impedance can be observed. In the case $r_b = 10$ mm no trapped modes are visible at the investigated frequencies. However, the same figure shows that for $r_b \geq 35$ mm, trapped modes start to appear. Further, the more r_b increases, the more the observed modes shift towards lower frequencies, and the more their impedance peak values rise. The key parameter of the phenomenon is the pipe radius ratio r_b/r_a . By increasing this ratio, the frequency of the resonant modes decreases, while their impedance peak value increases.

Figure 4.1: Configuration modelling an abrupt change in beam-pipe cross. Left: longitudinal impedance modulus computed for different values of r_b , at a fixed value of $r_a = 5$ mm. Right: geometry model with $L = 100$ mm.

A known solution to the problem is tapering. To investigate its effects, the geometry of Figure 4.1 was modified, by adding a conical connection of length L_t between the two pipes as is illustrated in Figure 4.2. The radius of the small pipe, the length of the pipes and the length of the conical taper were considered fixed ($r_a = 5$ mm, $L = 100$ mm, $L_t = 50$ mm) while the radius of the larger pipe, r_b was parametrized. The results of the simulations, that is the longitudinal impedance for different values of the radius r_b , is reported in Figure 4.2, left side. In the case $r_b > r_a$ there is an impedance increase in comparison to the case $r_b = r_a$, i.e. no change in cross section. This is the same qualitative behaviour as for the untapered configuration. For $r_b = 10$ mm no trapped modes are visible at the investigated frequencies. In this case virtually no differences can be found between tapered and not-tapered configurations. As for the configuration without taper of Figure 4.1, for $r_b \geq 35$ mm trapped modes start to appear, although the beneficial effects of the taper results in lower impedance peak values. Further, considering the r_b value which leads to the worst-case scenario (i.e. the highest considered r_b) the effects of variation in the taper length were investigated. The result is shown with a dashed line in Figure 4.2 (left side), revealing the beneficial effects of a longer taper which further decreases the peak impedance of the modes. A good practice in use at CERN is to have tapered transitions with a tapering angle not higher than 15 degrees [24], except if strictly required by the design.

Figure 4.2: Tapered section change configuration. Left: Longitudinal impedance modulus for different values of r_b . Right: geometry model with $r_a = 5$ mm, $L = 100$ mm, $L_t = 50$ mm.

Gap

Gaps and absence of electrical connections among components should be avoided. They create capacitive effects leading to high impedance values at low frequencies, which are very dangerous for RF heating. In order to study the gap effects, the geometry shown in Figure 4.3 right side was simulated. The length and the radius of the pipes were fixed ($r = 5$ mm and $L = 100$ mm), while the gap between the pipes, g , was parametrized.

Impedance simulation results are reported in Figure 4.3, left side, for different values of g . The capacitive effect of the gap results in high impedance at very low frequencies. The impedance peak values increase with the length of the gap. This is consistent with the results obtained in [25]. Other peaks at higher frequencies can be seen from the figure. According to [25], they map trapped modes in the gap.

The easy solution to the detrimental effects of a gap is the use of connections. Figure 4.4 shows the same geometrical layout as Figure 4.3, but with the addition of two symmetrical electrical connections between the two pipes. For simulations, the length and the radius of the pipes were considered fixed ($r = 5$ mm and $L = 100$ mm) while the gap between the pipe, g , was parametrized. The obtained results, reported on the left side of Figure 4.4, demonstrate the effectiveness of applying connections. Comparing the impedance of the open gap geometry with the impedance of the same geometry with connections, one notices that the impedance at very low frequencies is drastically reduced for all gap sizes when connections are added. However, in the connected geometry a new trapped mode is present, around 2 GHz, not found in the open gap configuration. This mode strongly depends on the contact shape and on the number of connection points and it can be shifted to higher frequencies by adding more contact points. The impedance behaviour for frequencies higher than 3 GHz seems not to be affected by the connections. During the design phase, gaps should always be avoided by some

kind of connections, and RF-fingers are usually used for this purpose. An example of their use can be found in Section 4.2, where the PSBAS is discussed.

Figure 4.3: Open gap model geometry. Left: longitudinal impedance modulus computed for different values of g . Right: geometry with $r = 5$ mm and $L = 100$ mm.

Figure 4.4: Gap with connections. Left: longitudinal impedance modulus for different values of g . Right: geometry with $r = 5$ mm and $L = 100$ mm.

Parasitic Cavities

Every empty volume that is directly seen by the beam potentially behaves like a parasitic cavity, i.e. it extracts energy from the beam, through the excitation of resonant modes. This leads to really high peaks in the impedance, which can prove extremely dangerous for long-range instabilities [26] and RF-heating. The bigger the empty volume is, the lower the mode's resonant frequency is. In general, if an empty volume is needed for to make a device work, it should be as small as possible. It is well recognized in the literature that in the case of a cavity, a key role is played by the wall material. Particularly the electrical conductivity strongly influences the peak impedance of the mode. The cavity geometry shown in Figure 4.5, right side, was simulated considering different wall materials. The longitudinal impedance modulus of the mode that resonates at the lowest frequency is reported in Figure 4.5, left side.

Figure 4.5: Unshielded cavity. Left: longitudinal impedance computed for different values of the material electrical conductivity σ . Right: geometry: $r_p = 60$ mm, $L = 800$ mm, $r_{bl} = 100$ mm, $L_c = 300$ mm, $r_c = 230$ mm.

The most common approach to eliminate this contribution is the use of RF shielding. An RF-shielding is a metal screen that blocks electromagnetic interactions between the beam and the empty volume. It can have different shapes in order to optimally fit the geometry it has to shield. An example of shielding is proposed in Figure 4.6, where the geometry of the previous parasitic cavity has been modified by adding ten metallic tubes on a circle connecting the inner pipe with the outer one. The results of the electromagnetic simulations on the shielded cavity geometry show a striking impedance reduction of about 6 orders of magnitude if compared with the results of the unshielded configuration. This is due to the fact that the particle beam no longer “sees” the empty volume, and the resonant mode disappears. A practical example of an RF-shielding can be found in the next section, where the PSBAS impedance design optimization is discussed.

Figure 4.6: Shielded cavity. Left: longitudinal impedance modulus computed for different values of the material electrical conductivity σ , on a logarithmic scale. Right: geometric model.

4.2 IMPEDANCE MINIMIZATION OF LIU DEVICES

This section summarizes the design studies for the new Proton Synchrotron Booster Absorber/Scraper (PSBAS), a device aimed at cleaning the beam halo at the very early stage of the PSB acceleration. The section outlines the steps performed to fulfil the design requirements and the design iterations for impedance optimization.

The Proton Synchrotron Booster Absorber Scraper

The PSBAS will represent the major aperture restriction of the PSB after 2020 [23]. It will scrape up to 6% of the total number of protons (2.95×10^{12} [23]) for a LIU beam during the very early stages of acceleration (kinetic energy per nucleon up to 200 MeV). It must be able to survive a direct accidental beam impact and its impedance has to be minimized. Further, in order to correctly scrape the beam halo, the PSBAS geometry has to follow the beam transverse envelope shape and its longitudinal evolution inside the device itself (the complete list of requirements can be found in the document [27]). To fulfil the outlined requirements the preliminary design shown in Fig. 4.7a was conceived.

The two graphite masks, cylinders with truncated squared based pyramid holes to follow the beam β function, one movable and the other fixed, are the actual beam scrapers. They can be positioned in two working configurations according to the operational requirements: retracting the movable mask provides a wide aperture for the initial beam commissioning while inserting the movable mask limits the aperture for an optimal beam cleaning during nominal operation. However, the preliminary design was found not optimal from an impedance perspective and it needed to be optimized.

Figure 4.7: Different views of the PSBAS. (a) Preliminary design in working configuration. (b) CST model.

To reduce the PSBAS impedance, an iterative loop was implemented starting from the initial PSBAS design, simulating the device impedance, identifying the problematic geometries, and modifying the mechanical drawing accordingly. The electromagnetic properties of the equipment were assessed through simulations with CST with the model shown in Fig. 4.7b.

To allow an easy motion of the movable graphite mask, the latter was not electrically connected to the rest of the device along the beam path direction. Thus, gaps were present in this design, leading to the generation of resonant electromagnetic modes, trapped in the gaps, as shown in Fig. 4.8a. Moreover, such a design presents an unshielded empty volume (parasitic cavity) around the fixed graphite mask shown in Fig. 4.7b.

It is important to stress that in the preliminary PSBAS design, some impedance mitigation measures were already taken: in the configuration mask out, the replacement vacuum chamber was acting as a shielding against the vacuum tank, preventing it from resonating as a parasitic cavity. However, this was not sufficient, and the impedance behaviour of the device turned out to be unacceptable. Indeed, trapped modes at frequencies lower than 0.4 GHz were found. The latter frequency is considered as the acceptable lower limit for modes in the PSB machine [28]. Therefore, the preliminary PSBAS design, was not impedance compliant. The impedance of the initial device is shown on the right side of Figure 4.8 with a dashed line.

Figure 4.8: (a) PSBAS preliminary design, electric-mode field shapes, with a maximum field strength of 500 V/mm. (b) Longitudinal impedance modulus in logarithmic scale of the preliminary and final (improved) design.

Some modifications to the PSBAS preliminary design were proposed in order to eliminate the low frequency resonant mode:

- Electric sliding connections, between movable and fixed parts, were added to eliminate the resonant modes in the gaps.
- The parasitic cavity was shielded by a geometry modification.

These modifications were implemented in the final PSBAS design reported in Figure 4.9. In the configuration mask out, the replacement vacuum chamber works as RF-shielding, preventing the tank to behave as a potential low-frequency parasitic cavity, trapping resonant modes. The electrical connections between the fixed mask housing and the “out pipe” (Figure 4.9, detail 2) shields the empty volume between the bellows and the housing itself, avoiding trapped resonating electromagnetic modes inside the housing. This connection is made by a ring made from stainless-

steel material with two copper spirals mounted on it, which is installed inside a circular groove, machined into the fixed mask housing. This allows for an easy assembly of the components and guarantees a good electrical contact at all times. The movable components, the replacement vacuum chamber and the movable mask with its housing, are separated from the fixed components, the pipe and the fixed mask housing, by a gap of 2 mm. However, they are electrically connected by means of sliding connections. As shown in Fig. 4.9, detail 1 and 3, there are copper wire spirals inserted into grooves realized on the replacement vacuum chamber and on the movable mask housing. They provide a path for the image currents and limit the detrimental effects of the trapped electromagnetic resonant modes in the gaps.

Figure 4.9: Design of the PSBAS with nomenclature and details of the electrical connections. The two working configurations are also shown: movable mask in (left) and movable mask out (right).

These solutions led to an impedance compliant design, eliminating the modes at low frequencies and decreasing the maximum impedance of the device by three orders of magnitude if compared with the previous performances. The longitudinal impedance of the final device is shown in Figure 4.8b (red

curve). Note that in both the final and preliminary PSBAS designs there are abrupt changes of cross section between the graphite masks and the pipes. No attenuation method was applied to reduce their effects because, due to operational and space constraints, it was impossible to add tapers. However, despite this, with the applied mitigation method, it was possible to drastically reduce the impedance at low frequencies.

4.3 IMPEDANCE AND THERMO-MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF HL-LHC DEVICES

Beam induced heating, or RF-heating, of components due to electromagnetic interactions between particles beam and equipment, is a crucial issue for high intensity/brightness particle accelerators. Taking the LHC as an example, RF-heating imposed severe limitations during its first operational run (2009-2013); some devices were damaged and numerous actions had to be taken to reduce the detrimental effects of RF-heating [29].

Electromagnetic beam-equipment interaction causes a power deposition proportional to the square of the beam intensity and to the real part of the device impedance [30] according to

$$\Delta P = I^2 \sum_{p=-\infty}^{p=+\infty} |\Lambda(p\omega_0)|^2 \text{Re}[Z_{\parallel}(p\omega_0)] \quad (24)$$

with Λ the normalized beam spectrum.

RF-heating can be split in two contributions:

- Resistive wall (RW) impedance heating. This phenomenon distributes the heat flux regularly over the device's walls according to the electric conductivity and permittivity and the magnetic permeability of the material and to the inverse of the beam-wall distance.
- Resonant modes (RM) heating. Due to the presence of trapped electromagnetic resonant modes in a device, the heat flux is distributed in a highly irregular way dependent on the mode field maps.

As a result, while the RW generates smooth temperature maps, RMs can lead to an uneven temperature distribution. Temperature gradients or power deposition in unexpected areas may induce intense mechanical stresses that can cause failures or generate other undesired effects such as material damage [31] and/or outgassing [32]. With the increase in beam intensity and the decrease in bunch length planned for the next generation of particle accelerators, the RF-heating phenomenon will be further intensified. Thus, this problem must be considered in the equipment design, particularly, for the Beam Intercepting Devices (BIDs). These are susceptible to severe RM and RW heating because they work in close proximity to the particle beam, their geometry is complex, and they are made from materials that have suboptimal electromagnetic properties. In this context, this section reviews a method that allows accurate simulations of the local thermo-mechanical effects due to the RF-heating [33] and presents an example application of this method to the "Target Dump Injection Segmented" (TDIS) [34].

THE METHOD

The current investigation defines a procedure to interface the two commercial programs CST and ANSYS mechanical® [35]. These tools are well known and tested at CERN: CST is a standard for device impedance computations, while ANSYS mechanical® is widely used for structural and thermal analysis. The former simulates the RF-heating map that is subsequently imported into the latter to calculate thermal and mechanical effects.

The entire procedure is shown in Figure 4.10. There are three main macro-areas: CST Electromagnetic Simulations (A, B and C blocks for RM heating and F input for RW heating), Beam Power Dissipation and Interface (D and E blocks), ANSYS Thermomechanical Simulations (G block). Every macro-area is divided in sub-blocks. Each of them will be explained taking as example the analysis performed for the Target Dump Injection Segmented (TDIS) [36]. The TDIS is a BID that will protect LHC downstream equipment during the injection phase, absorbing the injected beam in case of a misfiring injection kicker.

Figure 4.10: Block diagram of the methodology with some of the beam properties.

A: ELECTROMAGNETIC SIMULATIONS

The device CAD model for production is simplified and taken as geometric model for the electromagnetic simulations. Only the electromagnetic important elements are considered (screws, little grooves, small surfaces have been removed, see Figure 4.11 for example), in order to obtain an optimum balance between accuracy of the model and simulation speed.

Figure 4.11: TDIS CAD model, left, and simplified TDIS CAD model, right.

Subsequently, the presence of trapped RMs in the device is investigated through the CST eigenmode solver. The solver provides, for each RM, the resonating frequency f_m , the quality factor Q , the shunt impedance R_s , the local value of electric and magnetic fields and the surface currents in the entire geometry. After this has been accomplished, a second wakefield simulation is run. In this simulation, electric and magnetic field “monitors” are set at the resonant frequency of each RM obtained by the eigenmode solver, plus an electric and magnetic monitor at low frequency far from any resonant mode frequency. These last monitors are needed for the RW heating map, discussed later in this section.

As a first benchmark, the modes found by the two solvers (CST eigenmode and wakefield) should give the same resonant frequency, quality factor, and shunt impedance. If this is the case, the procedure can continue, otherwise the disagreement has to be investigated and fixed. Note that the beam can excite only a finite number of modes in the device because of its limited spectrum bandwidth.

B: THERMAL LOSS COMPUTATION

By processing the data from CST, the local dissipated power map for each mode can be obtained. The power dissipated by the m^{th} mode can be divided in:

- Losses per unit volume P_{Vm} [W/m³]: in this category one finds the resistive Joule losses, and losses found in ferromagnetic materials, due to eddy currents and magnetic hysteresis. The Joule and eddy currents losses can be computed using the first term on the right side of the following equation [37]:

$$P_{Vm}(x, y, z, f_m) = \sigma E_{rms}^2(x, y, z, f_m) + P_{VHm} \quad (24)$$

where σ is the electric conductivity of the material (frequency dependent) and E_{rms} is the root mean square value of the local electric field. More involved is the computation of P_{VHm} , the power dissipated by magnetic hysteresis in ferromagnetic material [38].

- Losses per unit surface P_{Sm} [W/m²]. Using the flux of the real part of the Poynting vector, one can compute the power dissipated within the walls of good conductors [39]:

$$P_{sm}(x, y, z, f_m) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi f_m \mu_0}{4\sigma}} |\vec{H}_t(x, y, z, f_m)|^2 \quad (25)$$

where \vec{H}_t is the local surface current vector and μ_0 is the vacuum permeability.

The CST software automatically computes both these local losses P_{sm} and P_{vm} using the data of the magnetic and electric field monitors.

C: DISSIPATED 3D POWER MAP

The results of the previous step can be mapped into the device model geometry using the CST thermal solver. This generates a 3D map of the power dissipated on the device by each RM. However, the map does not take into account the properties of the real beam that is passing through the device: beam revolution frequency and intensity, bunch shape, bunch length, distance between bunches and number of bunches. Indeed, the eigenmode solver calculates the electromagnetic field pattern without any applied excitation, while in the wakefield solver the excitation bunch is normalised to the bunch charge and it has to be rescaled with respect to the real beam that passes into the component. This implies that, while the 3D dissipated power distribution on the device is correct, the local absolute value is not. There is a scaling factor between the power dissipated by the actual beam and the one computed by the solvers.

D: DISSIPATED POWER SPECTRUM

To obtain this scale factor, the deposited power at a generic frequency $\Delta P(f)$ has to be evaluated by using the real beam characteristics:

$$\Delta P(f) = I^2 |\Lambda(f)|^2 \text{Re}[Z_{\parallel}(f)] \quad (26)$$

DISSIPATED POWER DUE TO RESONANT MODE

Since the simulated model is an approximation of the real one, the resonant frequency of the real modes in the device could slightly differ from the resonant frequencies of the simulated modes. This could have a huge impact on their dissipated power. Thus, a sensitivity analysis of this quantity should be performed. Using the eigenmode results, the device impedance due only to the resonant modes can be obtained. The single mode impedance is given by

$$Z_{\parallel}(f) = \frac{R_s}{1 + iQ \left(\frac{f_m}{f} - \frac{f}{f_m} \right)} \quad (27)$$

To study the sensitivity of the dissipated power with respect to the frequency of the resonant modes, several RM impedance profiles can be computed moving the resonant frequency of every single mode randomly within an arbitrary frequency range. This analysis should consider a statistically significant number of computed dissipated powers for different resonant frequencies.

Among all the obtained results, two cases should be analysed: the case of maximum induced power loss in the device and the average case. The former is to be chosen during the design phase of the device since it better represents a worst-case scenario, the latter should represent a more realistic scenario.

The maximum frequency shift can be set considering the geometrical simplifications done to the CAD model. Furthermore, if there are movable parts in the device, the frequency shift should also take into account this point. In real situations, the motion of the movable parts may be slightly different from the expected one because of the non-perfect control system accuracy. In simulations, usually, the motion is considered as perfectly coincident with the expected one. Thus, the difference in the real and the simulated configurations may lead to a frequency shift between the real and the simulated mode resonant frequency. As an example, for the TDIS, a frequency shift of ± 10 MHz was used. Figure 4.12 shows the TDIS longitudinal impedance, the HL-LHC beam normalized spectrum (BNS) and the dissipated power spectrum.

Figure 4.12. Power spectrum, beam normalized spectrum (BNS) and real part of the longitudinal impedance.

DISSIPATED POWER DUE TO RESISTIVE WALL IMPEDANCE

The RF-heating contribution of the RW has to be separated from the contribution of the RMs. This can be done by performing a further wakefield simulation with a modified geometry that eliminates the resonant modes in the frequency range of interest. The resulting broad band impedance is used in Eq. (24) to compute the RW heating.

E: 3D MAP RESCALING

For each mode, the surface and volumetric power distribution, P_{Sm} and P_{Vm} , are rescaled and added to the contributions of the other RMs to obtain the total volumetric power losses P_V and the total surface power losses, P_S . This is done according to the following relations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_S(x, y, z) &= \sum_{m=1}^{m=N} \Delta P(f_m) K_m P_{Sm}(x, y, z, f_m) \\
 P_V(x, y, z) &= \sum_{m=1}^{m=N} \Delta P(f_m) K_m P_{Vm}(x, y, z, f_m)
 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

where N is the number of RMs considered, and

$$K_m = \frac{1}{\iiint_V P_{Vm}(x, y, z, f_m) dV + \iint_S P_{Sm}(x, y, z, f_m) dS} \tag{29}$$

is the inverse of the total dissipated power computed by the CST solver, which represents the normalization factor of the power map.

F: THE RESISTIVE WALL IMPEDANCE HEATING

The RW power is distributed as a heat flux in the geometry according to the beam-wall distance and the electromagnetic properties of the wall material. A 3D map can be obtained in a wakefield simulation considering a magnetic and electric field monitor at very low frequency far from any resonant modes. The volumetric contributions of the RW heating are added to the total volumetric power losses $P_V(x, y, z)$ and the surface contributions are added to the total surface power losses, $P_S(x, y, z)$ as if RW heating was another resonant mode.

G: OUTPUT AND THERMO-MECHANICAL SIMULATIONS

To perform the thermo-mechanical simulations, the maps $P_V(x, y, z)$ and $P_S(x, y, z)$ are imported in the ANSYS workbench® and mapped as a surface heat load for good conductors or as volume heat load for dielectric and ferromagnetic materials.

The same geometrical model of the electromagnetic simulations should be used because every modification can lead to an inaccurate import of the impedance heating load. As validation, a steady state thermal simulation is done, the heating source is set as the P_V and P_S maps, and the cooling source is a fictitious convection on all the bodies. If the RF heat load is correctly imported, the power evacuated by convection must be the one expected from Eq. (26). If the evacuated power does not match the expected value of the imported power, this could be due to mesh issues since the mesh of the CST thermal solver and ANSYS should be highly similar. An example imported power map for the TDIS is shown in Figure 4.13. In Figure 4.14, the temperature map induced by the RF-heating in the TDIS is reported, and in Figure 4.15 the related mechanical stresses, due to the thermal differential expansion, are shown.

The analysis executed for the TDIS using this method allowed identification of critical areas in the TDIS and yielded as a final the conclusion that the design is safe because neither the temperature nor the mechanical stresses are above the melting point or the yield stresses, respectively [40].

Figure 4.13: Example of a mode RF-heating map imported in ANSYS®, for the TDIS core components.

Figure 4.14: Global temperature distribution of the TDIS.

Figure 4.15: Maximum mechanical stresses in the TDIS. These stresses, 85 MPa maximum, are not critical for the device; however, they are not negligible if compared with the yield stress of the material, 250 MPa.

4.4 HIGH TEMPERATURE SUPERCONDUCTING COATINGS

Superconductor (SC) properties form the basis of magnet performance for hadron machines. This is particularly important for the project of a future energy upgrade of LHC (High Energy LHC, HE-

LHC) and for the hadron option of FCC (FCC-hh). The main low-temperature superconductors (LTS) used in accelerator magnets are based on NbTi and Nb₃Sn. All SC magnets for colliders to-date have been based on a LTS material, NbTi, which has a critical field of about 11 T at 1.8K. NbTi-based accelerator technology has been pushed to its limit in the development of the LHC dipoles, with operating fields of 8.3 T at 1.9 K. Since then, accelerator magnet research has focused mostly on another low-temperature superconductor, Nb₃Sn, which has a much higher critical magnetic field of about 27 T at 1.8 K, and can provide access to fields beyond the intrinsic limitation of the NbTi technology. However, Nb₃Sn is a brittle inter-metallic compound, which imposes significant constraints on the design, fabrication and implementation of the material in accelerator magnets. Developments to improve the performance of this material are still in progress and there are expectations to reach maximum fields of about 17 T.

A fairly new area of conductor development pertains to high-temperature superconductors (HTS). These materials are under investigation for high-field magnet applications, and they could allow reaching magnetic fields above 20 T [41]. A strong effort is in progress in order to produce wires suited for HTS magnets with high current density. Another advantage of the use of HTS, in addition to reaching very high magnetic fields, is the possibility to remove the synchrotron radiation heat produced by the high-energy hadron beams at a higher temperature, thereby greatly reducing the power consumption due to the refrigeration process.

This promising technology has also been investigated for coating the beam screens of hadron machines, such as FCC-hh, a next-generation large hadron-hadron collider aiming for a 100 TeV center-of-mass proton-proton collision energy. Two counter-rotating proton beams, each carrying an average current of about 0.5 A will be kept in the ring by superconducting Nb₃Sn magnets generating a dipole field of 16 T at an operating temperature of 1.9 K. Each beam will emit about 28 W/m of synchrotron radiation in the arcs, a power that cannot be reasonably absorbed at a temperature of 1.9 K. The radiation can be instead conveniently absorbed by a 3 cm diameter beam screen, kept at 50 K.

At 50 K copper can, however, have relevant consequences on the beam stability. Indeed, the charged beam will generate image currents on the internal screen surface, that in turn produce wakefields that can strongly influence beam stability due to the resistive wall impedance. The entity of the effect is directly proportional to the surface impedance of the material facing the beam. In fact, the surface impedance for a single layer in the classical resistive wall case can be written as

$$Z_s = \frac{Z_0 \omega}{2c} \delta, \quad (30)$$

and, from Eqs. (17) and (18), we can see that Z_s is directly proportional to the resistive wall impedance.

The FCC-hh initial design considered a copper-coated screen in order to minimize impedance. The surface resistance of copper at 50 K may not be sufficiently low to guarantee a safe stability margin [42]. On the other hand, HTS materials seem to present a considerably reduced surface impedance with respect to copper at low temperature under high magnetic field. Therefore, this material can represent an important tool to reduce the resistive wall impedance of very large hadron machines.

However, a strong development of thin film and material technology and a characterization effort are needed in order to achieve the goals of HTS coatings for a large-scale facility such as the FCC-hh [43]. A reasonable first step in this direction would be to develop a surface impedance measurement facility for small-scale HTS films, able to operate in the temperature range 4.2-77 K, up to 16 T external applied magnetic field and at < 1 GHz frequency. This would serve the purpose of validating existing HTS thin film coating technologies and select the most promising materials, and promote the developments needed for the FCC-hh accelerator.

5. Mitigation techniques

In this chapter we review some important mitigation techniques that are used to counteract the impedance-induced instabilities. In particular, we focus on some methods adopted to deal with undesired collective effects for the future accelerator FCC-ee, and on the outcome of a workshop, also supported by ARIES, held in Zermatt, Switzerland, on 23-27 September 2019, dedicated to “Mitigation of Coherent Beam Instabilities in Particle Accelerators”.

In the previous sections we have already discussed some methods used to reduce the coupling impedance and to mitigate collective effects. In particular, we have discussed:

- 1) Actions on the geometry of the devices. We have investigated the following items:
 - a. The shape of the FCC-ee vacuum chamber. With the initially proposed elliptical geometry, the needed synchrotron radiation absorbers produced too high a coupling impedance. The solution was to change the geometry from elliptic to circular and to add lateral winglets in which the absorbers are placed. In this way the absorbers become almost invisible to the beam. The radius of the beam pipe has also been determined as a compromise between the electrical power requirement for the quadrupole magnets and the coupling impedance reduction.
 - b. The choice of the BPM geometry for FCC-ee. The conical buttons allow pushing the trapped modes to high frequencies. Moreover, by placing the BPM buttons at an angle of 45° allows eliminating a special type of winglet-to-circular tapers which yielded a very high coupling impedance.
 - c. The adoption, for FCC-ee, of bellows similar to those of comb-type used also in SuperKEKB. The RF shielding consists of nested teeth, which include small fingers to ensure electrical contacts.
 - d. Several methods were also discussed to reduce the impedance of some HL-LHC BIDs, such as: removing abrupt step transitions and using tapered transitions as much as possible; eliminating electrical discontinuities by means of RF contacts and shielding of parasitic cavities.
- 2) Actions on the material. For example, in order to cope with electron cloud effects, a NEG coating which reduces the secondary electron yield is necessary for FCC-ee. It has been demonstrated that the additional impedance due to the coating with respect to that of a single

layer of copper, under some assumptions generally satisfied for FCC-ee, is proportional to the thickness of the coating itself and does not depend on its conductivity. Therefore, instead of finding the exact conductivity of the coating, it is better, and sufficient, to determine the minimum thickness required to guarantee a good efficiency for the electron cloud effects.

- 3) Actions to avoid or suppress HOMs, as, for example, the work done for the FCC-ee interaction region.
- 4) Actions to mitigate collective effects. In this sense, for FCC-ee, we have seen that
 - a. beamstrahlung is a useful additional phenomenon, since it increases the microwave instability threshold; however, a self-consistent analysis taking into account, at the same time, the beam-beam and collective effects still needs to be performed;
 - b. we can use wigglers to increase the energy spread (see the FCC-ee booster). This has a beneficial effect for the single bunch instabilities, in particular for the microwave instability, but also in the transverse plane an increase of the longitudinal emittance reduces the collective effects.

Another important point to highlight is that, during the design stage, there should be a close interaction between mechanical engineers and electromagnetic experts. As discussed in Chapter 4, if actions are taken during the design stage by mechanical engineers, working on the drawings, in strict collaboration with electromagnetic experts, which evaluate the coupling impedance, it is possible to design an optimized structure from the beginning.

In the following two sections we first discuss a novel feedback system for future accelerators, in particular for FCC-ee, since, even if the rise time of the instability is comparable to that of other machines, due to the very large circumference, a few turns are sufficient for losing the beam. As a consequence, novel ideas and schemes are necessary to cope with this new regime. Finally, we summarise the output of the Zermatt workshop.

5.1 A NOVEL FEEDBACK SYSTEM FOR THE FCC LEPTON COLLIDER

In this section, two designs are proposed for the FCC-ee feedback system. The rise time of the transverse coupled bunch instability that has been obtained in Section 3.3 was about 2.3 ms. This rise time is not worse than that found in other running machines; however, for FCC-ee, due to the very large circumference, this corresponds to only about 7 machine turns, and for the booster this is even worse. This means that the feedback system has to act within a few turns and cannot have the same structure of those used up to now.

In order to design an effective feedback scheme able to provide a solution to the challenging problems of the FCC-ee beam dynamics, outlined in the previous sections, a multiple and distributed feedback approach is proposed. Furthermore, the system can be implemented by applying two different schemes, the first one maintaining the well-known feedback design with some modifications, the second one implementing an innovative and more complicated approach to apply correction signals after shortening the loop delay.

A question could arise: given that the instability growth is extremely fast, why does one not simply implement one feedback loop with a very high gain by using a large number of power amplifiers to obtain a faster damping time?

The answer, based on experience gained over the past twenty-five years, is the following: because the noise entering in the feedback pickup cannot be filtered completely. Consequently, the increasing of gain and power will produce an enlargement effect of the bunches, especially in the vertical beam dimension, and will push the feedback to an unavoidable saturation of the performance.

Design n.1: cooperating feedback systems

Considering a damping time of about 10 turns for each feedback system (the feasibility of which has already been demonstrated at other lepton colliders – namely at DAΦNE [44,45] and SuperKEKB [46,47] – for fractional betatron tunes more than 0.09 units away from the integer resonance), to cope with the instability speed foreseen by the simulations, it will be necessary to implement more feedback loops, most likely between 4 and 6. There are some drawbacks in this strategy because the larger number of kickers and pickups will increase the ring impedance. Another minor drawback will be given by the more complicated timing and setup operations.

An important advantage will be that of having the possibility to apply correction kicks distributed along the ring. There is a second advantage: indeed, by implementing this modular strategy, it could be possible to achieve, if necessary, the theoretical damping limit of 1 revolution turn by installing more feedback loops, maybe by implementing 10-12 stations. As said previously very low tune frequencies can lower the feedback performance in any case.

Figure 5.1: Example of cooperating feedback scheme implemented by 4 stations placed along the 100 Km long FCC ring. The projected damping time is 2.5 revolution turns.

Evaluating this scheme, it is obvious that a damping rate faster than 1 turn cannot be not achieved. This is because the correction kick can be applied only with 1 turn delay after processing the input signal. The feedback propagation delay cannot allow to kick faster. In Figure 5.1 an example of the cooperating feedback scheme is shown. For practical reasons, it could be implemented through 4 stations placed along the 100 km FCC ring. The expected damping time is 2.5 revolution turns.

Design n. 2: cooperating and “feeding forward” systems

Of course, the ring length is a critical point for managing the feedback in terms of timing and control of the correct performance of the system. Nevertheless, a 100 km ring length is a very interesting opportunity to design an innovative type of feedback system [48-52] that is not convenient and not even possible in smaller rings. The idea is to make the correction signal path shorter than 1 turn. In this way, it will be feasible to achieve damping rates even faster than 1 revolution turn.

The “feeding forward” approach will somewhat change the usual system scheme, however, not as much as it could seem. The phase response will be controlled by individual bunch FIR filters inside the DPU (digital processing unit) as usual.

This second kind of scheme would be a big challenge from a technological point of view to be implemented. It will be necessary to send the correction signal in such a way as to arrive to the kicker location before the arrival of the bunch that must be damped. As example, few cases are analysed below.

First, a “feeding forward” system can be designed that takes the input signal at the pickup 1 (PU1) and, after processing it in the station 1, sends the correction signal to the station 2 where kicker and power amplifier section are placed. The correction signal path follows the main ring diameter which is 31.8 km long. The foreseen damping time is 5 turns, half of the standard approach.

In Figure 5.2, the “feeding forward” system is implemented by two stations and two loops. The system 1 takes the input signal at the pickup 1 (PU1) and, after processing in the station 1, sends the correction signal at the station 2 where kicker 1 and power section 1 are placed. Vice versa the system 2 takes the input signal at the pickup 2 (PU2) and, after processing it in the station 2, sends the correction signal to the station 1 where kicker 2 and power amplifier section 2 are placed. The correction signal path is along the main ring diameter and it is 31.8 km long. The foreseen damping rate is 2.5 turns.

In Figure 5.3, a “feeding forward” system is implemented by one station and one loop. The system 1 takes the input signal at the pickup 1 (PU1) and, after processing it in the station 1, sends the correction signal to the station 2 where kicker 1 and power section 1 are placed. The correction signal path is on the chord related to a quarter of circumference arc and it is 22.5 km long. The foreseen damping rate is 2.5 turns.

Figure 5.2: “Feeding forward” system implemented by two stations and two loops. The correction signal path is on the main ring diameter and it is 31.8 km long. The foreseen damping rate is 2.5 turns.

Figure 5.3: “Feeding forward” system implemented by one station and one loop. The correction signal path is on the chord related to a quarter of circumference arc and it is 22.5 km long. The foreseen damping rate is 2.5 turns.

In Figure 5.4 the “feeding forward” system is implemented by four stations and four loops. The system 1 takes the input signal at the pickup 1 (PU1) and, after processing it in the station 1, sends the correction signal to the station 2 where kicker 1 and power section 1 are placed. The correction signal path is on the chord related to a quarter of circumference arc and it is 22.5 km long. The system 2, 3 and 4 similarly take the input signals at the PU2, PU3, PU4 and, after processing them in the station 2, 3 and 4, they send the correction signals to the station 3, 4 and 1 where kickers and power sections are placed. The foreseen damping rate in this case is 0.625 turns breaking the 1 turn limit with only four systems.

Figure 5.4: “Feeding forward” system implemented by four stations and four loops. The foreseen damping rate is 0.625 turns.

How to transmit the correction signal

Efficient correction data transmission is not a simple task. Solutions can be implemented by radio transmission, optical fibers or laser. Most likely the radio communication solution will be the simplest one because it does not need to occupy space on the ground. The distances are of the order of 22 or 32 km. In theory the chord length could be shorter than 22 km, however the arc path should be long enough to recover the digital feedback insertion delay of 400-600 ns plus cable delays.

Alternative approach: narrow band feedback in frequency domain

An alternative or complementary approach was suggested by A. Chao during eeFACT2018 (<http://eefact2018.ust.hk/>; another workshop co-supported by ARIES): Since the fastest instability rise times due to the resistive wall impedance correspond to the multi-bunch modes of lowest frequency, a dedicated feedback acting only in a narrow frequency band might help to specifically suppress the growth of one or few of these modes.

5.2 SUMMARY OF THE ICFA MINI-WORKSHOP ON "MITIGATION OF COHERENT BEAM INSTABILITIES IN PARTICLE ACCELERATORS"

The workshop in Zermatt, also sponsored by ARIES, focused on the cures of coherent beam instabilities, reviewing in detail the theories (with underlying assumptions), simulations and measurements on one hand, and trying to compare the different mitigation methods (for example with respect to other variables of interest such as the beam lifetime) to provide robust solutions for the machine operation on the other hand.

The workshop tried to answer some questions still open in this field, as, for example:

- Which tools do we have to ensure that new and upgraded machines are able to operate within their desired beam parameter range?
- Is the current modeling of the instabilities satisfactory or should it be improved in any of the cases?
- Are we covering all types of instabilities?
- What are the limits of currently deployed active feedback systems?
- Can we rank the methods introduced for stabilizing Landau damping?
- How far can we take impedance identification and reduction?
- Can we always disentangle the stabilizing effect of Landau damping from that of head-tail de-phasing?
- Are there alternative and efficient ways to introduce Landau damping (e.g. beam-beam collisions, electron lens, RFQ)?
- Can we exploit the new techniques of machine learning?
- Are there interactions between different mechanisms related to collective effects?

As an example, for the last question, let us consider the feedback systems used to damp instabilities: generally, they are working very well but they cannot, at the moment, damp all types of instabilities. In some cases, some destabilizing effects can also be observed [53].

The workshop was divided into 8 sessions:

Session 1: Review of beam instability mechanisms and modelling: impedance, electron cloud & ions, coherent beam-beam, two-particle models, two-mode models, Vlasov solvers, macroparticle codes.

Session 2: (1st mitigation method) - Landau Damping: Theory (and, in particular, approximations), applications, reasons for loss of Landau damping; BNS damping for linear accelerators.

Session 3: (2nd mitigation method) - "Operational knobs": Optics modifications (linear coupling, gamma transition, Q' , Q'' , etc.) for the transverse plane; RF changes for the longitudinal plane; effect of energy.

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- Session 4: (3rd mitigation method) - Feedback systems: technology, limitations, transverse, longitudinal.
- Session 5: (4th mitigation method) - Instability mechanism identification and reduction: impedance budget, impedance reduction, e-cloud suppression, space charge reduction, beam-beam reduction.
- Session 6: Role of diagnostics of instabilities in mitigations: Direct measurements of the incoherent tune spread and the stability diagrams, BTF, Schottky, wide band pick-ups, quadrupolar pick-ups, impedance localization, use of transverse damper as a controlled impedance.
- Session 7: Impact of mitigation methods and comparison: interplay between instability mitigations and incoherent effects, role of space charge, role of beam-beam, degradation of lifetime, synchro-betatron resonances.
- Session 8: Challenges for high intensity/brightness operation in future machines + closing remarks: many octupoles needed due to small beam sizes, damper in few turns, damper for intra-bunch motion, ultra-low impedance design, interplay between low impedance and e-cloud suppression.

Some presentations were dedicated, in particular, to the methods used to reduce accelerator impedances:

- M. R. Masullo, et al.: Metamaterial-based absorbers for the mitigation of beam coupling impedance effects (poster). As we have seen in Section 3.1, the resistive wall impedance constitutes a significant percentage of the total beam-coupling impedance budget of FCC-ee (and in general of many accelerators). Some reduction techniques have been discussed in the previous sections. A novel technique is the use of metamaterial-based absorbers that can sensibly reduce or nearly cancel resistive-wall impedance. Moreover, it is possible to design and fabricate sub-wavelength two-dimensional metallic resonant structures based on the split ring resonator (SRR) geometry that can be employed as mode dampers in accelerating structures. A number of prototypes are being fabricated and measured in a “test model” pillbox cavity. Experimental results agree well with full wave electromagnetic simulations and with the constitutive effective parameters of the SRR-based metamaterials retrieved using a numerical analysis. The study opens up the possibility of considering metamaterials as a valid alternative to other devices for impedance mitigation in experimental setups commonly operating along a particle beam line, such as accelerating cavities or collimators, and, more generally, for the development of filters with a large out-of-band signal rejection in specific applications.
- N. Biancacci, et al.: Impedance localization and identification. In already existing machine, before pursuing the reduction of machine impedance, it is important to identify the main sources of impedance. The localization of large coupling impedance sources allows focusing the mitigation efforts on the critical areas. Impedance localization measurements are

performed to quantify the transverse impedance from the global and local point of view. This type of measurement can be done in both bunched and coasting beams following different strategies and methods.

- E. Koukovini-Platia, et al.: Identification of the horizontal instability mechanism at the CERN Proton Synchrotron Booster. A horizontal head-tail instability has been observed in the CERN Proton Synchrotron Booster (PSB) since the '70s. Beam-based measurements of losses versus the horizontal working point revealed a dependence of the instability on the horizontal tune. Macro-particle simulations and the Vlasov solver suggested that an unmatched kicker termination was responsible for the observed beam losses and exponential growth. The extraction kicker was finally unambiguously confirmed to be the source of the instability. This was achieved with beam-based measurements with a temporarily modified termination, adjacent to the thyatron switch of the extraction kicker system, by replacing a high impedance termination, required for operation, with a matched termination using a 6.25 Ω resistor. In this modified configuration, no sign of the instability was any longer observed.
- R. Nagaoka: Optimization design and impedance sources in low emittance rings. There is a global trend today to go to chambers with much lower gaps to reach ultra-low emittance and high electron-beam intensity in future synchrotron light sources. In order to do that, strong quadrupole focusing is needed everywhere (in the range of 100 T/m instead of ~ 20 T/m in the present generation). This means reduced magnet bore radii and, as a consequence, smaller beam pipe half aperture. In addition to the small beam pipe radius, several other impedance contributions are present, such as tapers, BPMs, shielded bellows, flanges, cavities, kickers, absorbers, scrapers. Optimization and innovative vacuum components design, for example with new tapers to avoid cavity structures, or RF shielding foils in the button electrodes of BPMs, strongly help in suppressing the impedance of these devices.
- C. Zannini, et al.: Low-impedance design with example of kickers (including cables). Recently, unmatched terminations of single elements were identified as responsible of instabilities in the CERN-PSB and CERN-LEIR. Impedance models are needed to estimate the impedance of similar devices and to assess potential intensity limitations. Circuit model and simulation techniques which include the effect of coupling to cables on the beam coupling impedance have been investigated. Moreover, examples of low impedance design with special emphasis on the mitigation of ferrite kickers impedance (e.g. longitudinal serigraphy or coated ceramic inserts), optimization of transitions and shielding of unintentional cavities have been studied.
- S. Arsenyev: Low-impedance beam screen design for future colliders. Beam screen is increasingly more important in future colliders. In FCC-hh, it overshadows the collimators as the main source of impedance. A careful design of the geometry of the beam screen, in addition to a possible coating of the inner surface with a high-temperature superconductor, is giving very promising results, and further improvements are still possible. In addition, pumping hole screening is a very effective method for reducing their impedance. Finally, a new surface treatment for electron cloud mitigation, which could replace the coating with a low SEY material, is the laser surface engineering, a promising solution to mitigate electron cloud build-up, even if proper impedance measurements are still necessary to validate the concept.

- A. Mereghetti: Impedance reduction for (LHC) collimators. The collimation system is fundamental for the safe operation of a superconducting collider for high energy physics like the LHC. At top energy, the LHC collimators are the main contributors to the machine impedance budget. In the context of the HL-LHC project, the collimation system will be upgraded to lower its impedance footprint. This includes a change of the jaw material for the collimator families impacting impedance the most, with an R&D program to identify suitable materials and an improved collimator design, i.e. not only fulfilling impedance requests but also granting adequate beam cleaning and robustness against failures, by changing the present CFC (Carbon Fiber Composite) with materials of lower resistivity (Mo-coated materials) in secondary collimators.
- N. Wang: Mitigation of coherent beam instabilities in CEPC. The coherent beam instabilities in the Circular Electron Positron Collider (CEPC) are similar to those of FCC-ee. The main sources of coupling impedance can be divided into two kinds: components with large impedance contributions (such as resistive wall, RF cavities, electro-separators, vacuum transitions, IP chambers) and components with small impedances appearing in large numbers (flanges, bellows, pumping ports, BPMs). The impedances of the components are carefully designed and optimized. For the resistive wall contribution, the impedance is reduced with thinner NEG coating, RF shielding is adopted for cavity structures, taper transitions of 1/10 are used at aperture discontinuities, and HOM damping is considered for resonant structures. Finally, the effects of these impedances on the beam instabilities are evaluated.

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